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Dimensionality Reduction of Infrared Spectra using Variable Selection Algorithms with Fitness Functions adapted from Supervised Classification Methods. Application to the Identification of Spectroscopic Markers Discriminating the Maturity of Strawberries

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Abstract

The strawberries sector seeks rapid, economical, environmentally friendly and non-destructive technologies for monitoring external and internal changes in physical quality taking place in fruit during maturity, thus allowing fruit quality and nutritional requirements to be evaluated at any state. The use of portable Mid-Infrared (MIR) spectrometer based on micro-electro-mechanical systems has already been studied to assess the maturity state of strawberries. However, not all spectral information is valuable for adapted biomarker construction. The selection of wavenumbers has been addressed through several variable feature selection methods.

This work proposes to combine a Binary Grey Wolf Optimizer (BGWO), Binary Particle Swarm Optimizer (BPSO), Bee Colony Optimizer (BCO), Genetic Algorithm (GA), Ant Colony Optimizer (ACO), and Gravitational Search Optimizer (GSO) with supervised classification methods for an optimal detection of the maturity state of strawberries using MIR spectral data. The data represents 443 strawberry samples with 8 different maturity statuses divided into 36 strawberries of class 1 (Green), 34 of class 2 (White), 67 of class 3 (Red $\frac{1}{2}$) and class 4 (Red 1) each, 42 of class 5 (Red 2), 78 of class 6 (Red 4), 76 of class 7 (Red 6), and 43 of class 8 (Red 8). A new fitness function in the six feature selection algorithms mentioned above is proposed in this work which is the error rate of supervised classification methods such as Naïve Bayesian Classifier (NBC), Decision Tree Classifier (DTC), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The suggested algorithms are called BGWO-NBC, BGWO-DTC, BGWO-LDA, BGWO-SVM, BPSO-NBC, BPSO-DTC, BPSO-LDA, BPSO-SVM, BCO-NBC, BCO-DTC, BCO-LDA, BCO-SVM, GA-NBC, GA-DTC, GA-LDA, GA-SVM, ACO-NBC, ACO-DTC, ACO-LDA, ACO-SVM, GSO-NBC, GSO-DTC, GSO-LDA, GSO-SVM.

The performance of Self-Organizing Map (SOM) Neural Network classification for the MIR spectra of maturity of strawberries at wavenumbers selected by the feature selection algorithms has been tested using four levels of cross-validation that splits the data into training set, validation set, and test set. The results of SOM Neural Network classification prove that GA-LDA allow better discrimination across the three levels of cross-validation splits within the maturity process than advanced methods which take into account the number of wavenumbers selected by other combination of algorithms. Classification accuracies are 94.6% for 25% test set, 98.1% for 15% test set, and 99% for 10% test set. BGWO-SVM attained the best performance in the 20% test set split with 95.5%. Moreover, feature selection algorithms allowed better classification for the 8 classes of maturity of strawberry than the original dataset.

Keywords: Supervised Dimensionality Reduction, Machine Learning, Metaheuristic Optimization, Swarm Intelligence, Fitness Function, Mid-infrared Spectra, Strawberry Maturity.

Resume

Le secteur de la fraise recherche des technologies rapides, économiques, respectueuses de l'environnement et non destructives pour surveiller les changements externes et internes de la qualité physique des fruits au cours de la maturité, permettant ainsi d'évaluer la qualité des fruits et les besoins nutritionnels dans n'importe quel état. L'utilisation d'un spectromètre portable Mid-Infrared (MIR) est basée sur des systèmes micro-électro-mécaniques a déjà été étudiée pour évaluer l'état de maturité des fraises. Cependant, toutes les informations spectrales ne sont pas utiles pour la construction de biomarqueurs adaptés. La sélection des nombres d'onde a été traitée par plusieurs méthodes de sélection de caractéristiques variables.

Ce travail propose de combiner un optimiseur binaire de loup gris (BGWO), un optimiseur binaire d'essaim de particules (BPSO), un optimiseur de colonie d'abeilles (BCO), un algorithme génétique (GA), un optimiseur de colonie de fourmis (ACO) et un optimiseur de recherche gravitationnelle (GSO) avec des méthodes de classification supervisées pour une détection optimale de l'état de maturité des fraises à l'aide de données spectrales MIR. Les données représentent 443 échantillons de fraises avec 8 statuts de maturité différents répartis en 36 fraises de classe 1 (Vertes), 34 de classe 2 (Blanche), 67 de classe 3 (Rouge 1/2) et classe 4 (Rouge 1) chacune, 42 de classe 5 (rouge 2), 78 de classe 6 (rouge 4), 76 de classe 7 (rouge 6) et 43 de classe 8 (rouge 8). Une nouvelle fonction de fitness dans les six algorithmes de sélection de caractéristiques mentionnés ci-dessus est proposée dans ce travail. Machine à vecteurs de soutien (SVM). Les algorithmes suggérés sont appelés BGWO-NBC, BGWO-DTC, BGWO-LDA, BGWO-SVM, BPSO-NBC, BPSO-DTC, BPSO-LDA, BPSO-SVM, BCO-NBC, BCO-DTC, BCO-LDA, BCO-SVM, GA-NBC, GA-DTC, GA-LDA, GA-SVM, ACO-NBC, ACO-DTC, ACO-LDA, ACO-SVM, GSO-NBC, GSO-DTC, GSO-LDA, GSO-SVM.

Les performances de la classification du réseau neuronal de la carte auto-organisée (SOM) pour les spectres MIR de maturité des fraises aux nombres d'onde sélectionnés par les algorithmes de sélection de caractéristiques ont été testées à l'aide de quatre niveaux de validation croisée qui divisent les données en ensemble d'apprentissage, ensemble de validation, et ensemble de test. Les résultats de la classification SOM Neural Network prouvent que GA-LDA permet une meilleure discrimination entre les trois niveaux de séparation de validation croisée au sein du processus de maturité que les méthodes avancées qui prennent en compte le nombre de nombres d'ondes sélectionnés par d'autres combinaisons d'algorithmes. Les précisions de classification sont de 94.6% pour un ensemble de tests à 25%, de 98.1% pour un ensemble de tests à 15% et de 99% pour un ensemble de tests à 10%. BGWO-SVM a atteint les meilleures performances dans l'ensemble de test de 20% avec 95.5%. De plus, les algorithmes de sélection de caractéristiques ont permis une meilleure classification pour les 8 classes de maturité du fraisier que l'ensemble de données original.

Mots clés : Réduction de Dimensionnalité Supervisée, Apprentissage Automatique, Optimisation Métaheuristique, Intelligence en Essaim, Fonction de Remise en Forme, Spectres Infrarouges Moyens, Maturité de la fraise.

List of Abbreviations

ACO	Ant Colony Optimizer
AUC	Area Under Curve
BCO.....	Bee Colony Optimizer
BGWO.....	Binary Grey Wolf Optimizer
BP	Back Propagation
BPSO.....	Binary Particle Swarm Optimizer
CV	Cross-Validation
DTC.....	Decision Tree Classifier
EMSC	Extended Multiplicative Signal Correction
FPR.....	False Positive Rate
GA	Genetic Algorithm
GSO.....	Gravitational Search Optimizer
LDA.....	Linear Discriminant Analysis
MIR	Mid-Infrared
ML.....	Machine Learning
NBC.....	Naive Bayesian Classifier
PCA.....	Principal Component Analysis
ROC.....	Receiver Operating Characteristic
Se.....	Sensitivity
SI	Swarm Intelligence
SOM	Self-Organizing Map
Sp.....	Specificity
SVM	Support Vector Machine
TPR.....	True Positive Rate

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1. Introduction

Scientists, engineers, economists, and managers always have to take many technological and managerial decisions for construction and optimization of any system. Day by day the world becomes more and more complex and competitive in decision making. With the explosive development of massive data, it is difficult to analyze and extract high level knowledge. The increasing trend of high-dimensional data collection and problem representation calls for the use of dimension reduction as a preprocessing technique before many machine learning tasks. Dimension reduction refers to techniques that reduce the number of input variables in a dataset. More input features often make a predictive modeling task more challenging to model, more generally referred to as the curse of dimensionality. High-dimensionality statistics and dimensionality reduction techniques are often used for data visualization. Nevertheless, these techniques can be used in applied machine learning to simplify a classification or regression dataset in order to better fit a predictive model. Machine learning is the most commonly used technique to address larger and more complex tasks by analyzing the most relevant information already present in databases. Machine learning is programming computers to optimize a performance criterion using example data or past experience. The selection of relevant features and elimination of irrelevant ones are the key problems in machine learning that have become an open issue. To overcome high-dimensional data problems, researchers use mainly two approaches. The first one is feature extraction, which comprises the creation of a new feature space with low dimensionality by combining features from the original feature set. The second one is feature selection that focuses primarily on removal of irrelevant and redundant features of the original feature set.

In a smaller scope, feature selection techniques are classified into three categories filter, wrapper and embedded methods. Filter methods are independent of learning or classification algorithm. It always focuses on the general characteristics of the data. Wrapper methods always include the classification algorithm and interact with the classifier. These are computationally expensive methods than the filter and also provide more accurate results as compared to filter methods. Embedded methods are a combination of filters and wrapper methods. In embedded methods, the feature selection is a part of the training process and which is held with the classifier. Wrapper approaches present better results in comparison with filter methods, but they are slower than filters methods. Wrapper methods depend on the modelling algorithm in which every subset is generated and then evaluated. Subset generation in wrapper methods is based on the different search strategy. Search techniques are differentiated into three categories; exponential, sequential and randomized selection strategy. In the exponential method, the number of evaluated features increases exponentially with the size of features. Although this method shows accurate results, it is not practically possible to apply because of the high computational cost. Sequential algorithms include or remove features sequentially. Once a feature is included or removed in the selected subset, it cannot be further changed that leads to local optima. Randomized algorithms include randomness to explore the search space, which saves the algorithms from trapping into local optima. Randomized algorithms are commonly known as population-based approaches. The main categories of randomized algorithms are simulated annealing, random generation, and metaheuristic algorithms. **Figure 1** presents the categorization of methods for solving feature selection. The dashed line box indicates the methodology of the study.

Figure 1: Flow chart of categorization of methods for solving feature selection.

Metaheuristic algorithms are optimization methods that obtain the optimal (near-optimal) solution of optimization problems. These algorithms are derivative-free techniques and, have simplicity, flexibility and capability to avoid local optima. The behavior of metaheuristic algorithms is stochastic; they start their optimization process by generating random solutions. It does not require to calculate the derivative of search space like in gradient search techniques. The metaheuristic algorithms are flexible and straightforward due to the simple concept and easy implementation. The algorithms can be modified easily according to the particular problem. The main property of metaheuristic algorithms is that they have a remarkable ability to prevent the algorithms from premature convergence. Due to the stochastic behavior of algorithms, the techniques work as a black box and avoid local optima and explore the search space efficiently and effectively. The algorithms make a tradeoff between its two main essential aspects exploration and exploitation. In the exploration phase, the algorithms investigate the promising search space thoroughly, and exploitation comes for the local search of promising area(s) that are found in the exploration phase.

Switching to the biological part, one of the challenges of the twenty-first century is to achieve a more productive agriculture, while improving the safety and quality of food. Climatic conditions, such as temperature and light intensity, and other preharvest factors, e.g., soil type, fertilization, irrigation, mulching, and other cultural practices, have a significant effect on many fruit maturities such as avocados, oranges, apples, kiwis and strawberries, and consequently on their quality. For example, the kiwifruit is kind of climacteric variant fruit who's the flavor and texture change over time. In addition, the accurate evaluation of avocado harvest maturity is one of the important aspects determining avocado fruit postharvest quality. On the other hand, over-mature fruit will have short shelf life and are more susceptible to postharvest physiological disorders and diseases, resulting to major economic losses. Strawberry fruit quality depends on different sensory characteristics such as color, appearance, texture, mechanical properties, etc. Studies have been conducted to assess for predicting the initial internal quality of strawberries and for discriminating between different classes of fruits produced by different fertility management systems. Currently, strawberry producers and handlers are lengthening shelf life through early harvesting of firm fruit with less developed color. Maturity indices are important

for deciding when to harvest strawberries. Sugars and organic acids have an important impact on the sensory quality of strawberry fruit. However, traditional techniques of analysis of some characteristics of such samples cannot be realized in situ at large scale. One idea that emerges is to replace them by spectroscopic techniques since it is possible to design portable spectrometers with specific bands that can be used to measure and analyze in situ characteristics of fruits in a non-destructive way.

Mid-infrared spectroscopy has a number of advantages over the traditional methods, as it (i) is a method of non-destructive analysis, (ii) does not pollute the environment, because it does not use chemical reagents, (iii) is cheap and fast, (iv) measures many parameters in a single analysis, and (v) can perform analyses in situ and online for a large number of samples per minute. MIR spectroscopy provides information on the modes of vibration of the studied sample, amplitude variations of specific wavenumbers being an indicator of the molecular changes. Fundamental molecular vibrations are related to the MIR absorption. In the field of agriculture industry, the evolution of biomarkers corresponding to intrinsic characteristics of plants and to their indices of maturity have been ensured by MIR that represents a growing factor at this level. However, not all spectral information is valuable for the construction of biomarkers, while the use of limited number of *a priori* wavenumbers may be tricky.

The strawberry sector is increasingly demanding methods for the monitoring of fruit quality parameters throughout the ripening process, with a view to identifying the optimal harvesting time depending on the final destination of the product. For this reason, we have used a portable mid-infrared spectrometer based on micro-electro-mechanical system to measure strawberries maturity spectra. The principal objective in this master thesis is to combine metaheuristic optimization algorithms and classification methods to select MIR spectral wavenumbers that optimize the classification of the state of maturity process of strawberries spectra measured with a handheld spectrometer. New fitness functions based on the concept of the supervised classification model are proposed and evaluated in this work. The fitness is basically the error rate of classification methods.

The plan for this work is as follows:

In the first part, we present what Feature Selection is and its associated algorithms. Then, we detail the operating principle of population-based metaheuristic algorithms. We focus more particularly on Swarm Intelligence (SI) algorithms, Gravitational Search Optimization, and Genetic Algorithm, and their detailed operation which allows the selection of relevant features.

In the second part of this work, we present machine learning algorithms used to calculate the fitness value for the Metaheuristic algorithms. We go deep in the description of supervised classification methods such as Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), Naïve Bayes Classifier (NBC), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Decision Tree Classifier (DTC). We also explain the Cross-Validation (CV) sampling technique which is used in 4 split modes. At the end of this part, we present the Self-Organizing Map (SOM) Neural Network classification method which is used as a supervised classification method for the state of maturity process of strawberries.

In the third part, we present the results obtained by applying our metaheuristic-machine learning algorithms combination on the 8 strawberry classes (class1: Green; class2: White; class3: Red^{1/2}; class4: Red1; class5: Red2; class6: Red4; class7: Red6; class8: Red8). We show that the results observed allow us to pick the most valid models, which are the GA-LDA and BGWO-SVM, implemented with the SOM Neural Network classifier.

Finally, and after discussing the results, we close with a general conclusion on the interest of the combination of feature selection algorithms with machine learning methods, its capability and performance in dimension reduction, and on the possibilities of implementing other tools belonging to metaheuristic algorithms to improve the accuracy rates.

2. Literature Review

In the last five decades, several effective metaheuristic algorithms have been designed to solve different kinds of feature selection and optimization problems.

Various techniques have been employed to select optimal subsets of wavenumbers from spectra [1, 2, 3]: successive-projections algorithm, backward/forward-selection algorithm, competitive adaptive reweighted sampling, variable importance for projection, uninformative-variable elimination, interval partial least squares regression, Monte Carlo-uninformative variable elimination, competitive adaptive reweighted sampling - partial least squares (CARS-PLS), simulated annealing, artificial neural network-based methods, particle-swarm optimization, variable importance in partial least squares projection, loading weights, regression coefficient, sequential search, etc. [4]. For example, CARS-PLS models showed significantly higher robustness and accuracy for prediction of multispecies pulp wood feedstock properties using lowest variable numbers [1]. The interval partial least square algorithm has been used to select waveband to predicted with the dry matter in kiwifruits [5]. However, most of these techniques need an additional a priori complementary information such as concentrations [1, 6] may be not well adapted to extensive data sets.

A growing class of metaheuristic-optimization computations that became popular are the Genetic Algorithms (GA) [7]. GA are deeply powerful methods employed in several band selection problems, including agriculture-related applications [8]. For example, it allows to discriminate plant species [9] or to evaluate the biodegradation of lignocellulosic biomass [10]. The combination of GA with Neural Network (GANN) for multi-class was used to predict the ripeness grades of oil palm fresh fruit using Near Infrared spectral data [11]. Moreover, the combination of GA with partial least square, as a variable selection method, have shown their potential for modeling with good precision two quality parameters, the total acid and the soluble solid contents, of *Flos Lonicerae Japonicae* [12].

Moving to Swarm Intelligence (SI), the most popular algorithm in this category is the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). PSO was introduced by Kennedy [13] in 1995. Researchers proposed different variants of PSO. One of them is the Binary version. It has been efficient in agriculture-related applications such as the work of Mohd Saiful Azimi Mahmud [14] where he applied the BPSO, which is a binary variant of PSO, and GA to find the shortest routing path for spraying operations in a greenhouse. The results indicated the performance of the GA was better for solution quality and computational time, while binary PSO performed better with respect to convergence time. Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) is a recent swarm intelligence technique proposed by Seyedali Mirjalili [15]. Like the PSO, the GWO has many improvements and variants. Binary versions are the most used such as the work conducted by S.P. Manikandan [16] where experiments revealed the capabilities of the BGWO to explore features space for the optimal features combination for gene selection from microarray data to classify cancers and genes related to cancer with accuracy of 95.45%. Another novel swarm intelligence is the Bee Colony Optimization (BCO) developed by D. Karaboga [17] in 2005. In his work, Haixia Sun [18] used the BCO to improve his model (successive projections algorithm-least squares-support vector machine) in obtaining accurate and synchronous detection of the soluble solid contents (SSC) in fresh jujubes at different stages of maturity to get a determination coefficient of 0.98, root-mean-square error equals to 1.24%, and a residual predictive deviation of 6.96 after having these values as 0.98, 1.19%, 7.25 respectively. His research

demonstrated that the combination of hyperspectral imaging and the BCO had good application values in the testing of agricultural products. Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) is one of the efficient SI algorithms proposed by Marc Dorigo in his Phd thesis work in 1992. ACO has been used in various domains especially as a tool in wavelength selection where Mojtaba Shamsipur [19] proved that ACO possesses a great ability to find best subsets of wavelengths, at a short period of time with small PRESS values, via accumulation of information in the form of pheromone trails deposited on each wavelength. Results obtained by the introduction of ACO clearly revealed the improved predictive ability in wavelength selection over the original full-spectrum models.

Gravitational Search Optimization (GSO) [20-21-22] proposed by Esmat Rashedi (2009) have attracted the attention of more and more scholars and can effectively solve many scientific problems. Bao-Chang Xu [23] implemented an improved GSO that uses trial-and-error method to update the optimal agent during the whole search process in the field of dynamic neural network identification. Compared to the original GSO the improved version shows the best performance. Sikander Singh Cheema [24] applied GSO to predict the suitable soil for good production of the crop. The proposed model utilizes a quantum value-based gravitational search optimization (GSO) to optimize the best solution. Extensive experiments show that the proposed model achieves an optimal selection of crops.

Regarding the Mid-Infrared (MIR) spectroscopy data, Camila Assis [25] tested four variable selection methods including GA for the development of models to determine Robusta-Arabica coffee blends. The number of selected variables in the optimized models varied from 6.5 to 17.0% of the total number of original variables which demonstrates the importance of feature selection techniques. Fangfang Chen [26] used Principal Component Analysis (PCA) followed by PSO-SVM, backpropagation (BP), Decision Tree (DT) on glioma Mid-infrared spectra. The classification accuracy of the three models was 92.00 %, 91.83 %, 87.20 %, and the AUC values were 0.919, 0.945, and 0.866, respectively. The results show that PCA-PSO-SVM has a better classification effect.

Taking into account the previous work, the objective of this thesis work is to compare the performance of different metaheuristic algorithms applied to Mid-Infrared spectroscopy data of strawberry fruits taking into consideration the error rate of supervised machine learning methods as the fitness function.

3. Feature Selection

3.1 Definition

Since 1970's, feature selection has been an active and fruitful field of research area in pattern recognition, machine learning, statistics and data mining communities. The main objective of feature selection is to choose a subset of input variables by eliminating features, which are irrelevant or of no predictive information. It is a process that selects the best features from the datasets. Feature selection has proven in both theory and practice to be effective in enhancing learning efficiency, increasing predictive accuracy and reducing complexity of learned results. Feature selection is one of the most critical and challenging problems in machine learning. The various applications of the feature selection problem can be demonstrated in different fields. There are some applications such as biomedical problems, text mining, image analysis, text processing of internet documents, gene expression array analysis, and combinatorial chemistry.

Feature Selection is basically defined as the process of finding the best informative feature subsets in order to escape the scourge of dimensionality and maximize the classification accuracy. The idea for feature selection is to be able to determine the best attributes that are suitable to the classification task. The feature selection process has two main steps: subset generation and subset evaluation. The general procedure for feature selection technique is illustrated in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: General feature selection process

Mathematically, a feature selection problem can be formulated in the following way: Assume a dataset 'S' contains 'd' number of features. Then the working mechanism of feature selection problem is to select relevant features among 'd' features. Given dataset $S = \{f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_d\}$. The objective is to select the best subset of features from S. Extract Subset $D = \{f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n\}$ where, $n < d$ and $f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n$ represents the features of any dataset.

Figure 3: Feature selection representation

We can sum up the advantages of feature selection in the following five points:

- Space required to store the data is reduced as the number of dimensions comes down.
- Less dimensions lead to less computation/training time.
- Some algorithms do not perform well when we have a large dimension. So, reducing the dimension needs to happen for the algorithm to be useful.
- It takes care of multicollinearity by removing redundant features. Hence, there is no point in storing multiple features as just one of them does what you require.
- In some cases, other than classification, it helps in visualizing data. It is very difficult to visualize data in higher dimensions so reducing our space to 2D or 3D may allow us to plot and observe patterns more clearly.

Feature selection is considered as a preprocessing technique used before feeding any model or classification problem. Whereas the preprocessing stage is the first stage for implementing any machine learning algorithm, the latter is a subset of a larger research field called Artificial Intelligence (AI).

3.2 Different types of feature selection

As previously described, feature selection refers to a fairly large class of machine learning preprocessing techniques. According to the tools used and the different methods used, it is possible to distinguish 3 sub-classes of Feature Selection:

- Filter methods for feature selection where the selection of features is independent of any machine learning algorithms. Instead, features are selected on the basis of their scores in various statistical tests for their correlation with the outcome variable. The correlation is a subjective term here. These methods evaluate how much the attributes are relative to the problem by checking properties of the data without developing learning

algorithms. Generally, a feature relevancy score is calculated and then the small scoring features are removed. Subsequently, high ranked features are performed as an input to the classification process. Such methods include Pearson correlation, Linear Discriminant Analysis, Analysis of variance, Chi-square, etc.

- Wrapper methods for feature selection try to use a subset of features and train a model using them. Based on the inferences that we draw from the previous model; we decide to add or remove features from your subset. The problem is essentially reduced to a search problem. Wrapper methods select the features by taking into account each probable subset of them and the features subsets are ranked in keeping with their extrapolative influence, whereas considering the inbuilt classifier as a recorder. It considers the relevance and redundancy information of the features in additionally to their impacts at the predictive strength. It makes use of a specific learning algorithm to assess the value of the chosen attributes. These methods are usually computationally very expensive. Such methods include exponential search strategy, sequential search strategy, and randomized search strategy. Specified a predefined learning rule, a general work flow of the wrapper techniques is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: A general framework of wrapper models

- Embedded methods for feature selection combine the qualities of filter and wrapper methods. It's implemented by algorithms that have their own built-in feature selection methods. Some of the most popular examples of these methods are LASSO and RIDGE regression which have inbuilt penalization functions to reduce overfitting.

In this thesis work we will focus on a specific category within the randomized search strategy wrapper methods which is the Metaheuristic optimization algorithms.

3.3 Metaheuristic Algorithms

Most (if not all) real-life problems can be formulated as optimization problems. To solve optimization problems, different methods have been studied in mathematical programming, operations research, and so on. Conventional methods, however, are usually not efficient enough when the problem space is large and complex. Many problems faced in artificial intelligence are combinatorial optimization problems. To solve these problems efficiently, different "heuristics" have been used to "search for the sub-optimal solution". Heuristics are search methods produced based on human's intuitive and creative thinking, and are often useful in local search to find good solutions quickly in a restricted area. Metaheuristics are higher level heuristics that control the whole process of search, so that global optimal solutions can be

obtained systematically and efficiently. Although metaheuristics cannot always guarantee to obtain the true global optimal solution, they can provide very good results to many practical problems. Usually, metaheuristics can enhance the computing power of a computer system greatly without increasing the hardware cost.

Metaheuristic frameworks are defined in general terms, metaheuristic algorithms can be adapted to fit the needs of most real-life optimization problems in terms of expected solution quality and allowed computing time, which can vary greatly across different problems and different situations. Secondly, metaheuristics do not put any demands on the formulation of the optimization problem (like requiring constraints or objective functions to be expressed as linear functions of the decision variables). However, this flexibility comes at the cost of requiring considerable problem-specific adaptation to achieve good performance. Metaheuristic algorithms classification is more detailed in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5: Different Metaheuristic Optimization Algorithms

A Meta-heuristic is formally defined as an iterative generation process which guides a subordinate heuristic by combining intelligently different concepts for exploring and exploiting the search space, learning strategies are used to structure information in order to find efficiently near-optimal solutions. In the designed algorithm, a solution vector is represented by (10101100) this implies that 1 means that a particular feature is selected and 0 means that feature is

not selected in the subset. Meta-heuristic algorithms are among these approximate techniques which can be used to solve complex problems.

3.3.1 Theoretical foundations of metaheuristic optimization

Two opposite criteria should be taken into account in development of a metaheuristic algorithm: (1) exploration of the search space and (2) exploitation of the best solution (**Figure 6**). Promising areas are specified by good solutions obtained. In intensification, the promising regions are explored accurately to find better solutions. In diversification, attempts are made to make sure that all regions of the search space are explored. In the exploration approach, random algorithms are the best algorithms for searching. Random algorithms generate a random solution in each iteration and completely exploit the search space in this way.

Figure 6: Metaheuristic algorithm design space

3.3.2 Initial population

The algorithms start the optimization process with generating a set of random solutions (individuals) in the search space to formulate the initial population. Each individual consists of a set of candidate features (feature subset). Each individual is a binary vector, with N features, where N is the number of features in the dataset; where 0 means that the corresponding feature is unselected, while 1 means that the feature is selected.

3.3.3 Objective function

The objective function, also known as fitness function, generates a real number for any solution in the search space. This number describes the quality or the fitness of the solution. The objective function is an important element in development of a metaheuristic algorithm that directs the search toward the best solution. If the objective function is wrongly defined, it will generate unacceptable solutions. Since the core purpose of the proposed algorithms is to effectively enhance the performance and results of the classification algorithm, we proposed the minimization of the objective function which is the error rate generated by supervised classification algorithms and we are considering random search algorithms which are numerical optimization methods independent of the gradient and hence can be used for noncontinuous or nondifferentiable functions. The objective function defines the relative importance of a design. Since our fitness value is the error rate of the supervised classification methods, a lower fitness value implies a better design.

3.3.4 Classification of metaheuristic algorithms

Deterministic or stochastic: Deterministic metaheuristic algorithms solve optimization problems through deterministic decision-making (such as local search and tabu search). In stochastic metaheuristic algorithms, several stochastic rules are applied to searching. In deterministic algorithms, the initial solution leads to the generation of a final solution similar to the initial one.

Population-based vs. single-point search algorithms: Single-point algorithms (such as simulated annealing) direct and transmit a single solution throughout the search process, while population-based algorithms (such as particle swarm optimization) will involve the whole solution population. Single-point search algorithms apply an exploitive approach; these algorithms have the power to concentrate searching on the local space. Population-based algorithms have exploratory trajectory and allow for more diversified exploration of the search space.

Iterative or greedy approach: In iterative algorithms, the search starts with an initial set of solutions (population), and the solutions vary in each iteration. In greedy algorithms, the search begins with a null solution, and a decision variable is determined at each step until the final solution is obtained. Most metaheuristic algorithms follow an iterative approach.

Algorithms discussed in this thesis work are all random, iterative, stochastic, and population-based algorithms.

Researchers pay great attention to metaheuristic algorithms because of their characteristics. Several algorithms have been designed and solved different types of problems. Based on their behavior, the metaheuristic algorithms can be divided into three main categories; evolution-based, swarm intelligence based, and physics-based.

(1) Evolution based algorithms: It is inspired from the natural evolution and start their process with randomly generated population of solutions. In these types of algorithms, the best solutions are put together to create new individuals. The new individuals are formed using mutation, crossover and select the best solution. The most popular algorithm in this category is Genetic algorithm (GA) that is based on Darwin evolution technique. There are other algorithms such as evolution strategy, genetic programming, tabu search, differential evolution.

(2) Swarm intelligence-based algorithms: These algorithms are inspired by the social behaviors of insects, animals, fishes or birds etc. The most popular technique is Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) developed by Kennedy and Eberhart. It is inspired by the behavior of a group of birds that fly throughout the search space and find their best location (position). Ant colony optimization, bee colony optimization, monkey optimization are examples of swarm intelligence algorithms.

(3) Physics based algorithms: These are inspired by the rules of physics in the universe. Simulated annealing, Harmony search come under physics-based algorithms.

3.4 Swarm Intelligence (SI)

Swarm Intelligence (SI) has attracted interest from many researchers in various fields. SI is the collective intelligence behavior of self-organized and decentralized systems, e.g., artificial groups of simple agents. Two fundamental concepts that are considered as necessary properties of SI are self-organization and division of labor. Self-organization is defined as the capability of a system to evolve its agents or components in to a suitable form without any external help. Self-organization relies on four fundamental properties of positive feedback, negative feedback, fluctuations and multiple interactions. Positive and negative feedbacks are useful for amplification and stabilization respectively. Fluctuations meanwhile are useful for randomness. Multiple interactions occur when the swarms share information among themselves within their

searching area. The second property of SI is division of labor which is defined as the simultaneous execution of various simple and feasible tasks by individuals. This division allows the swarm to tackle complex problems that require individuals to work together.

3.4.1 Feature Selection Using Binary Grey Wolf Optimizer (BGWO)

Binary Grey Wolf Optimizer (BGWO) is a recent swarm intelligence algorithm that has been successfully employed for solving Feature Selection problems. Many characteristics distinguished BGWO from other SI algorithms. It has few parameters to tune, a good balance between exploration and exploitation can be achieved in simple way and a favorable convergence can be reached. Moreover, BGWO is simple, easy to use, flexible, and scalable. The main inspiration of BGWO is the intelligence of leadership and hunting behaviors of the grey wolves in nature. Usually, wolves live in packs with strict hierarchy; the leader of the pack called alpha (α), and its responsible of leading the entire pack in hunting, migration, and feeding. In the second level of the hierarchy, a beta (β) wolf is located, which replace α in leading the pack in case its ill, or dead, followed by delta wolves (δ). The rest of the pack is called omegas (Ω). **Figure 7** shows the hierarchy of wolves in the pack, where alphas are the most powerful wolves and omegas are the least power.

Figure 7: Social hierarchy of wolves in BGWO

The second inspiration of BGWO is how grey wolves hunt the prey. The hunting process is accomplished in a set of steps; chasing, encircling, harassing, and attacking.

In hunting process, alphas recognize a prey, then the team track, chase, and approach it. Then, they encircle and harass the prey until it halts. The wolves keep moving towards the prey until they become very close, then α and β wolves start attacking. At this moment, deltas and omegas

are waiting, in case the prey escaped they update their positions according to the prey's new position. Due to the social hierarchy of wolves, the best three wolves (α , β , and δ) supposed to have more knowledge about the location of the prey than omegas. Therefore, all wolves should update their positions according to the positions of α , β , and δ . By repeating the encircling and hunting operators, the best location (prey) can be located.

The mathematical model of BGWO is formulated as follows:

Definition 1 The distance between each wolf and the prey (eq. 1)

$$\vec{D} = |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{X}_p(t) - \vec{X}(t)| \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

$$\vec{C} = 2 \cdot \vec{r}_1 \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

where $\vec{X}_p(t)$ and $\vec{X}(t)$ represent the position vector of the prey and a wolf respectively, and t represents the current iteration, \vec{C} is coefficient vector, calculated as in (eq. 2), \vec{r}_1 is a random vector in the interval $[0, 1]$.

Definition 2 Recognizing prey's location (eq. 3)

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = \vec{X}_p(t) - \vec{A} \cdot \vec{D} \quad (\text{eq. 3})$$

$$\vec{A} = 2 \cdot \vec{a} \cdot \vec{r}_2 - \vec{a} \quad (\text{eq. 4})$$

$$a = 2 - 2\left(\frac{t}{T_{max}}\right) \quad (\text{eq. 5})$$

where A is a coefficient vector, \vec{a} is a linearly decreased coefficient from 2 to 0 over the optimization process, and \vec{r}_2 is a random vector inside $[0,1]$.

Definition 3 Updating the wolves positions:

$$\vec{D}_\alpha = |\vec{C}_1 \cdot \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{X}| \quad (\text{eq. 6})$$

$$\vec{D}_\beta = |\vec{C}_2 \cdot \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{X}| \quad (\text{eq. 7})$$

$$\vec{D}_\delta = |\vec{C}_3 \cdot \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{X}| \quad (\text{eq. 8})$$

$$\vec{X}_1 = \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{A}_1 \cdot (\vec{D}_\alpha) \quad (\text{eq. 9})$$

$$\vec{X}_2 = \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{A}_2 \cdot (\vec{D}_\beta) \quad (\text{eq. 10})$$

$$\vec{X}_3 = \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{A}_3 \cdot (\vec{D}_\delta) \quad (\text{eq. 11})$$

$$\vec{X}(t+1) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } S\left(\frac{\vec{X}_1 + \vec{X}_2 + \vec{X}_3}{3}\right) \geq r_3 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{eq. 12})$$

Figure 8: Updating the wolf new position

where \vec{r}_3 is a random vector in $[0, 1]$ and S is the sigmoid function having a S-shaped form as it can be seen in **Figure 9**, and it can be expressed as:

$$S(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(10(x-0.5))}} \quad (\text{eq. 13})$$

Figure 9: Sigmoid function

As described in Eq. (4), by decreasing the weights of \vec{a} from 2 to 0 in the interval $[2, 0]$, the values of \vec{A} will be limited into the interval of $[-2a; 2a]$. The wolves can scan any context between their current situation and the location of intended victim when the \vec{A} is inside $[-1,1]$. The movement rule of wolves in the case of $|A|<1$ or $|A|>1$ is demonstrated clearly in Figure 8. When $|A|>1$, all population perform the wide-spread hunting motions in order to detect all possible locations of the prey and fruitful areas of the search space. Hence, when $|A|>1$, the BGWO give more stress to exploration tendencies. When $|A|<1$, the predators will concentrate on the neighbourhood of the potential preys with decreased step sizes. During exploration and exploitation phases, the randomized C values can increase the chance of BGWO in escaping from the local optima and stagnation drawbacks. It also enriches the random spirit of the hunting inclinations in BGWO. The effect of $|A|$ is shown in **Figure 10**.

Figure 10: Impact of $|A|$ on the movement vectors

The fitness function used to evaluate the wolves is given as:

$$F_i^{BGWO} = F^{BGWO}(\mathbf{z}_i) = R_i^{classifier} \quad (\text{eq. 14})$$

Where $R_i^{classifier}$ shows the classifier error rate.

3.4.2 Feature Selection Using Binary Particle Swarm Optimization (BPSO)

Binary Particle Swarm Optimization (BPSO) has been shown as an effective approach for searching optimal final feature subsets. One of the problems with BPSO-based feature selection methods is that they relinquish the number of features in their search processes while they only emphasize maximizing the classification accuracy. Another limitation is to select similar features in the final feature subset. Moreover, the existing PSO-based methods do not use correlation information of the features to guide the search process probability to be selected in the good features in during iteration, which increase the classifier performance. BPSO involves the personal best (pbest) and global best (gbest) solutions in the velocity and position update. For each particle (solution), the velocity is updated as:

$$v_i^d(t+1) = wv_i^d(t) + c_1r_1(pbest_i^d(t) - x_i^d(t)) + c_2r_2(gbest_i^d(t) - x_i^d(t)) \quad (\text{eq. 15})$$

where v is the velocity, x is the solution (position of particle), w is the inertia weight, c_1 and c_2 are the acceleration factors, r_1 and r_2 are two independent random numbers in $[0,1]$, pbest is the personal best solution, gbest is the global best solution for the entire population, i is the order of particle in the population, d is the dimension of search space, and t is the number of iterations. Afterward, the velocity is converted into probability value using (eq. 16), and the position of particle is updated as shown in (eq. 17):

$$S(v_i^d(t+1)) = \frac{1}{1+\exp(-v_i^d(t+1))} \quad (\text{eq. 16})$$

$$x_i^d(t+1) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } rand < S(v_i^d(t+1)) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{eq. 17})$$

where $rand$ is a random number uniformly distributed between 0 and 1. Iteratively, the $pbest$ and $gbest$ are updated as follows:

$$pbest_i(t+1) = \begin{cases} x_i(t+1) & \text{if } F(x_i(t+1)) < F(pbest_i(t)) \\ pbest_i(t) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{eq. 18})$$

$$gbest(t+1) = \begin{cases} x_i(t+1) & \text{if } F(pbest_i(t+1)) < F(gbest(t)) \\ gbest(t) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{eq. 19})$$

where x is the solution, $pbest$ is the personal best solution, $gbest$ is the global best solution for the entire population, $F(\cdot)$ is the fitness function, and t is the number of iterations.

Thus, the proposed fitness function is considered the classification accuracy (see eq. 20). Since the classification accuracy is to be minimized, the classifier error rate, which is the complement of the classification accuracy, is used in the fitness function

$$F_i^{BPSO} = F^{BPSO}(z_i) = R_i^{classifier} \quad (\text{eq. 20})$$

Where $R_i^{classifier}$ shows the classifier error rate.

3.4.3 Feature Selection Using Bee Colony Optimization (BCO)

Bee Colony Optimization (BCO), also known as Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm, is motivated from the intelligent food foraging behavior of honey bee insects. Honey bee swarm is one of the most intelligent swarms exists in nature; which follows collective intelligent method, while searching the food. The honey bee swarm has many qualities like bees can communicate the information, can memorize the environment, can store and share the information and take decisions based on that. According to changes in the environment, the swarm updates itself, assigns the tasks dynamically and moves further by social learning and teaching.

Figure 11: Sketch representing Bee Colony Optimization

The search process of BCO follows three major steps:

- Send the employed bees to a food source and calculate the nectar quality;
- Onlooker bees select the food sources after gathering information from employed bees and calculating the nectar quality;
- Determine the scout bees and employ them onto possible food sources.

The locations of the food sources are arbitrarily selected by the bees at the initial stage and their nectar qualities are measured. The employed bees then share the nectar information of the sources with the onlooker bees waiting at the dance area within the hive. After sharing this information, each employed bee returns to the food source checked during the previous cycle, as the location of the food source had been recalled and then selects new food source using its observed information in the neighborhood of the present food source. At the last stage, an onlooker bee uses the information retrieved from the employed bees at the dance area to select a good food source. The possibility for the food sources to be elected boosts with boost in its quality of nectar. Hence, the employed bee with information of a food source with the highest quality of nectar employs the onlookers to that food source. It afterward chooses another food source close by the one presently in her memory depending on observed information. A new food source is randomly generated by a scout bee to replace the one abandoned by the onlooker bees. This complete search process could be outlined in **Figure12** .

Figure12 : Phases in Bee Colony Optimization

3.4.3.1. Initialization of Swarm

The BCO algorithm has three parameters: the number of food sources (population), the number of tests after which a food source is treated to be jilted (limit) and the termination criteria (maximum number of cycle). In the original BCO, the number of food sources is equal to the employed bees or onlooker bees. Initially it considers an evenly dealt swarm of food sources (SN), where each food source x_i ($i = 1, 2 \dots SN$) is a D-dimensional vector. Each food source is generated using following method:

$$x_{ij} = x_{minj} + rand[0,1](x_{maxj} - x_{minj}) \quad (\text{eq. 21})$$

Where $rand [0,1]$ is a function that generates an evenly distributed random number in range $[0,1]$.

3.4.3.2. Employed Bee

Employed bees phase update the present solution based on the information of individual experiences and the fitness value of the newly found solution. New food source with higher fitness value replaces the existing one. The position update equation for j^{th} dimension of i^{th} candidate during this phase is shown below:

$$V_{ij} = x_{ij} + \varphi_{ij}(x_{ij} - x_{kj}) \quad (\text{eq. 22})$$

Where $\varphi_{ij}(x_{ij} - x_{kj})$ is known as step size, $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, SN\}$, $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, D\}$ are two randomly chosen indices. $k \neq i$ ensure that step size has some indicative improvement.

3.4.3.3. Onlooker Bee

The number of food sources for onlooker bee is same as the employed. During this phase all employed bee share fitness information of new food sources with onlooker bees. Onlooker bees calculate the selection probability of each food source generated by the employed bee. The best fittest food source is selected by the onlooker. There are number of methods for calculation of probability, but it must include fitness. Probability of each food source is decided using its fitness as follow:

$$P_i = \frac{fit_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{SN} fit_i} \quad (\text{eq. 23})$$

3.4.3.4. Scout Bee Phase

If the location of a food source is not updated for a predefined number of cycles, then the food source is assumed to be neglected and scout bees phase is initialized. During this phase the bee associated with the neglected food source converted into scout bee and the food source is replaced by the arbitrarily chosen food source inside the search space. In BCO, the predefined number of cycles is an important control parameter which is called limit for rejection. Now the scout bees replace the abandoned food source with new one using following equation:

$$x_{ij} = x_{minj} + rand[0,1](x_{maxj} - x_{minj}) \quad (\text{eq. 23})$$

$$\forall j=1,2,\dots,D$$

3.4.4 Feature Selection Using Ant Colony Optimization (ACO)

ACO algorithm is a kind of swarm intelligence algorithm. By simulating the process of ant colony foraging, the shortest path in different environments is established by using the internal information transmission mechanism of ant colony. In the process of activity, ants will leave pheromone, and the subsequent ants can choose the path according to the pheromone left by the previous ants. The higher the concentration of pheromone remaining on the path, the higher the probability that the ant will choose this path. At the same time, the concentration of pheromone will volatilize with time. Therefore, through the ant colony behavior, ants continuously learn and optimize through the information feedback mechanism to determine the shortest foraging path. The flow chart of the ACO algorithm is illustrated in **Figure13**.

Figure13 : The Flow Chart of the ACO algorithm

Each ant randomly starts at a node and visits the other nodes according to the transition rule. The learning procedure is to update the pheromone information repeatedly.

(1) The transition rule:

In the route, the k^{th} ant starts from node i , the next node j is selected among the unvisited nodes memorized in J :

$$j = \begin{cases} \arg \max_{l \in N_i^k} \left\{ \left[\tau_{il} \right] \left[\eta_{il} \right]^\beta \right\}, & q \leq q_0, \\ J(p_{ij}^k), & q > q_0, \end{cases} \quad (\text{eq. 24})$$

where q is a random variable uniformly distributed in $[0, 1]$, q_0 is a parameter for the best possible move ($0 \leq q_0 \leq 1$), k is an ant, β is a parameter which determines the relative influence of the heuristic information, η_{il} is the heuristic information value, i, j are the initial and the next choice or candidate, l is a candidate solution, N_i^k is the feasible neighborhood of ant k , J is a random variable obtained according to the probability distribution P_{ij}^k (see (eq. 25)) in which the ant k chooses the next solution if $q > q_0$. If $q \leq q_0$ it means that the ant is exploiting the learned knowledge based on the pheromone trails and the heuristic information.

If $q > q_0$ the ant explores other tours or search around the best-so-far solution. The probability distribution is expressed as follows:

$$p_{ij}^k = \frac{[\tau_{ij}]^\alpha [\eta_{ij}]^\beta}{\sum_{i \in N_i^k} [\tau_{il}]^\alpha [\eta_{il}]^\beta} \quad (\text{eq. 25})$$

where α is a parameter which determines the relative influence of the pheromone trail.

(2) The second rule is the Global Pheromone Trail Update, which is given by:

$$\tau_{ij} \leftarrow (1 - \rho)\tau_{ij} + \rho \Delta\tau_{ij}^{bs}, \quad \forall (i, j) \in T^{bs} \quad (\text{eq. 26})$$

where ρ is the global pheromone evaporation rate ($0 < \rho \leq 1$), $\Delta\tau_{ij}^{bs}$ is the amount of pheromone the ant k deposits on each best-so-far solution and T^{bs} is a set of the best connections. When this rule is applied, both the evaporation and new pheromone deposit are update only to the best-so-far ant.

Local Pheromone Trail Update, the last rule, is applied during the tour construction. The pheromone evaporation and a new pheromone deposit are updated when an ant is exploiting or exploring the connection according to the pseudorandom proportional rule, given by:

$$\tau_{ij} \leftarrow (1 - \xi)\tau_{ij} + \xi \tau_0 \quad (\text{eq. 27})$$

where ξ is the local pheromone evaporation rate ($0 < \xi < 1$), and τ_0 is the initial pheromone trails value.

The effect of the local updating rule, is that each time an ant uses an arc (i, j) or connection, its pheromone trails τ_{ij} is reduced and, therefore, the arc becomes less attractive for the following ants.

3.5 Feature Selection Using Gravitational Search Optimization (GSO)

The Gravitational Search optimization algorithm is based on the law of gravity. In this algorithm, agents are considered as objects and their performance is measured by their masses. All these objects attract each other by the gravity force, and this force causes a global movement of all objects towards the objects with heavier masses. Hence, masses cooperate using a direct form of communication, through gravitational force. The heavy masses – which correspond to good solutions – move more slowly than lighter ones, this guarantees the exploitation step of the algorithm. In GSO, each mass (agent) has four specifications: position, inertial mass, active gravitational mass, and passive gravitational mass. The position of the mass corresponds to a solution of the problem, and its gravitational and inertial masses are determined using a fitness function. In other words, each mass presents a solution, and the algorithm is navigated by properly adjusting the gravitational and inertia masses. By lapse of time, we expect that masses be attracted by the heaviest mass. This mass will present an optimum solution in the search space. The GSO could be considered as an isolated system of masses. It is like a small artificial

world of masses obeying the Newtonian laws of gravitation and motion. More precisely, masses obey the following laws:

- Law of gravity: each particle attracts every other particle and the gravitational force between two particles is directly proportional to the product of their masses and inversely proportional to the distance between them, R . We use here R instead of R^2 , because according to our experiment results, R provides better results than R^2 in all experimental cases.
- Law of motion: the current velocity of any mass is equal to the sum of the fraction of its previous velocity and the variation in the velocity. Variation in the velocity or acceleration of any mass is equal to the force acted on the system divided by mass of inertia.

Figure 14: Flow Chart representing the GSO Algorithm

Now, consider a system with N agents (masses). We define the position of the i^{th} agent by:

$$X_i = (x_i^1, \dots, x_i^d, \dots, x_i^N) \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

where x_i^d presents the position of i^{th} agent in the d^{th} dimension.

At a specific time 't', we define the force acting on mass 'i' from mass 'j' as following:

$$F_{ij}^d(t) = G(t) \frac{M_{pi}(t) \times M_{aj}(t)}{R_{ij}(t) + \varepsilon} (X_j^d(t) - X_i^d(t)) \quad (\text{eq. 28})$$

where M_{aj} is the active gravitational mass related to agent j , M_{pi} is the passive gravitational mass related to agent i , $G(t)$ is gravitational constant at time t , ε is a small constant, and $R_{ij}(t)$ is the Euclidian distance between two agents i and j :

$$R_{ij}(t) = \|X_i(t) - X_j(t)\|_2 \quad (\text{eq. 29})$$

To give a stochastic characteristic to our algorithm, we suppose that the total force that acts on agent i in a dimension d be a randomly weighted sum of d^{th} components of the forces exerted from other agents:

$$F_i^d(t) = \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N rand_j F_{ij}^d(t) \quad (\text{eq. 30})$$

where $rand_j$ is a random number in the interval $[0, 1]$.

Hence, by the law of motion, the acceleration of the agent i at time t , and in direction d^{th} , $a_i^d(t)$ is given as follows:

$$a_i^d(t) = \frac{F_i^d(t)}{M_{ii}(t)} \quad (\text{eq. 31})$$

where M_{ii} is the inertial mass of i^{th} agent.

Furthermore, the next velocity of an agent is considered as a fraction of its current velocity added to its acceleration.

Therefore, its position and its velocity could be calculated as follows:

$$V_i^d(t+1) = rand_i \times V_i^d(t) + a_i^d(t) \quad (\text{eq. 32})$$

$$X_i^d(t+1) = X_i^d(t) + V_i^d(t+1) \quad (\text{eq. 33})$$

where $rand_i$ is a uniform random variable in the interval $[0, 1]$. We use this random number to give a randomized characteristic to the search.

The gravitational constant, G , is initialized at the beginning and will be reduced with time to control the search accuracy. In other words, G is a function of the initial value (G_0) and time (t):

$$G = G_0 e^{-\nu \frac{t}{T_{max}}} \quad (\text{eq. 34})$$

Where ν is an arbitrary constant and T_{max} is the maximum number of iterations. Gravitational and inertia masses are simply calculated by the fitness evaluation. A heavier mass means a more efficient agent. This means that better agents have higher attractions and walk more slowly. Assuming the equality of the gravitational and inertia mass, the values of masses are calculated using the map of fitness. We update the gravitational and inertial masses by the following equations:

$$M_{pi} = M_{ai} = M_{ii} = M_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (\text{eq. 35})$$

$$m_i(t) = \frac{fit_i(t) - worst(t)}{best(t) - worst(t)} \quad (\text{eq. 36})$$

$$M_i(t) = \frac{m_i(t)}{\sum_{j=1}^N m_j(t)} \quad (\text{eq. 37})$$

where $fit_i(t)$ represent the fitness value of the agent i at time t , and, $worst(t)$ and $best(t)$ are defined as follows (for a minimization problem):

$$best(t) = \min_{j \in \{1, \dots, N\}}(fit_j(t)) \quad (\text{eq.38})$$

$$worst(t) = \max_{j \in \{1, \dots, N\}}(fit_j(t)) \quad (\text{eq. 39})$$

3.6 Feature Selection Using Genetic Algorithm (GA)

Genetic algorithm (GA) is mathematical technique used in computing to find true approximate solutions. It is well adapted for optimization problems. Genetic Algorithms are a class of evolutionary algorithms that use techniques inspired by evolutionary biology such as inheritance, mutation, selection and crossover. The steps of proposed GA methodology are shown in **Figure 15**. These algorithms are based on the concept of natural selection of solutions by copying its main principles. Each solution may be considered a population, where each element is represented by a chromosome built with selected wavenumbers positioned as genes. The GA steps reproduce various evolutionary operations, such as crossover and mutation, allowing the method to select for each generation the best chromosomes and to identify at the end an optimal chromosome with respect to an optimization criterion defined by a fitness function.

Figure 15: Synoptic of the GA methodology with binary genes. In our case, genes correspond to wavenumbers

Genetic Algorithm steps

Let $\mathbf{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be a matrix of MIR spectral data of dimension $\mathbb{R}^{S \times n}$ where each column corresponds to an infrared spectrum extracted at S wavenumbers $\mathbf{W} = [w_1, \dots, w_S]^T \in \mathbb{R}^S$ where S is the number of spectral bins. Spectra are recorded on several samples belonging to a set of classes $\mathcal{C} = \{c_1 \dots c_k \dots c_K\}$. The idea behind GA is the use of a population of solutions, each one represented in the form of a chromosome with selected wavenumbers positioned as genes. These algorithms are a type of evolutionary optimization computation based on the concept of natural selection of solutions in each generation for reproduction and various evolutionary operations such as crossover and mutation.

The initialized parameters are: the chromosome size L (the number of genes corresponding to the bands to be selected); the population size N (the number of chromosomes per generation); the number of elites N_e (the number of chromosomes with the best fitness values in the current generation that are guaranteed to survive to the next generation); and the fraction $FRAC_c$ (the number of chromosomes selected to perform crossover N_c such that $N_c = FRAC_c(N - N_e)$). The stopping parameters are the maximal number of iterations T_{max} , and the tolerance ϵ for the chosen fitness function.

The first step of a GA is the creation of the starting population $P(0)$. N chromosomes are generated by randomly selecting L wavenumbers from \mathbf{W} ($L < S$ is the size of the chromosomes):

$$P(0) = \left\{ \mathbf{z}_i = [z_{i1}, \dots, z_{iq}, \dots, z_{iL}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^L \right\}_{i=1}^N \quad (\text{eq. 40})$$

The initial population $P(0)$ of wavenumbers variables is chosen randomly from the set of uniformly distributed variables ranging over their maximum and minimum limits has been stated as:

$$\mathbf{z}_i^0 \sim U(\mathbf{z}_i^{\min}, \mathbf{z}_i^{\max}) \quad (\text{eq.41})$$

where \mathbf{z}_i^0 signifies the initial l th variable of the i^{th} population; \mathbf{z}_i^{\min} and \mathbf{z}_i^{\max} are the minimum and maximum limits of the l th decision variable; $U(\mathbf{z}_i^{\min}, \mathbf{z}_i^{\max})$ signifies a uniform random variable ranging over $[\mathbf{z}_i^{\min}, \mathbf{z}_i^{\max}]$.

Then each chromosome \mathbf{z}_i in the current population is evaluated using a fitness function $F(\cdot)$ that assigns a fitness value F_i :

$$F_i = F(\mathbf{z}_i), \forall i = 1 \dots N \quad (\text{eq. 42})$$

The fitness function is arguably the most important part of a GA. The role of a fitness function is to measure the quality of the chromosome in the population according to the given optimization objective. In our case, the fitness function will assess the state of maturity process of strawberries spectra.

The error rate of supervised machine learning method is one of the simplest methods that can be used as a classical fitness function with which to evaluate the clusters. This function maximizes the separability of K classes. The fitness function is defined as follows:

$$F_i^{GA} = F^{GA}(\mathbf{z}_i) = R_i^{\text{classifier}} \quad (\text{eq. 43})$$

where $R_i^{\text{classifier}}$ is the error rate of the model classifier such as NBC, LDA, SVM and DTC.

For each fitness function F_i , the values are ordered in ascending order and the best N_c chromosomes are selected based on this ordering. These are the surviving chromosomes that will be copied unchanged in the next population.

Once this selection has been completed, other N_p chromosomes are selected in pairs to replicate and to form $N_c = N_p$ "child" chromosomes in the next population. The selection is performed probabilistically so that an individual's selection probability is proportional to the individual's fitness. There are several schemes for the selection process: roulette-wheel selection and its extensions, scaling techniques, tournament models, elitist models, ranking, proportional selection, stochastic methods and stochastic universal sampling selection, etc. In our application, we have chosen the universal sampling selection procedure since this method is a single-phase sampling algorithm that has no deviation between the expected reproduction rate and the algorithmic sampling frequency and has a minimum spread. First, we compute the probability p_i of selecting the chromosome \mathbf{z}_i and the cumulative probability q_i :

$$p_i = \frac{F_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N F_i} \quad (\text{eq. 44})$$

$$q_i = \sum_{k=1}^i p_k \quad (\text{eq. 45})$$

Next, we generate a uniform random number $r \in [0, 1/N]$. If $r < q_1$, we select the first chromosome z_1 ; otherwise, we select the chromosome z_i such that $q_{i-1} < r \leq q_i$.

Once the selection of N_p chromosomes has been completed, to form child chromosomes, we apply the crossover technique that is a structured yet randomized information exchange between chromosomes. This process allows the production of two children from two parents. In this process, genetic material from one parent is combined with genetic material from another parent to discover better children. Crossover operators can be realized by many methods, including single-point, k-point, Flat, uniform and/or order-based, discrete, and nonlinear methods. This work used a uniform crossover since it gives good results and has been used successfully in a majority of cases. A uniform crossover operator combines a uniform blend of data from each parent, promoting greater exploration. In uniform crossover, each gene is randomly selected either from the first or from the second parent.

To explain the uniform crossover of genetic algorithms, the parent's chromosomes $p_1[\mathbf{z}_{iq}]$, $p_2[\mathbf{z}_{iq}]$ and the children's chromosomes $o_1[\mathbf{z}_{iq}]$, $o_2[\mathbf{z}_{iq}]$, $q = 1 \dots L$ are gene arrays. The most popular crossover variant between real numbers is the uniform crossover. Genes situated in the q position of the children's chromosomes \mathbf{z}_i are calculated as it follows:

α is a random vector of real numbers uniformly distributed with the same size as p_1, p_2, o_1, o_2 where $\alpha_q \in [0,1]$:

Children are copied from parents and crossover is obtained with equations (46) and (47):

$$o_1[\mathbf{z}_i] = p_1[\mathbf{z}_i],$$

$$\text{for each } \alpha_q > 0.5, o_1[\mathbf{z}_{iq}] = p_2[\mathbf{z}_{iq}] \quad (\text{eq. 46})$$

$$o_2[\mathbf{z}_i] = p_2[\mathbf{z}_i],$$

$$\text{for each } \alpha_q > 0.5, o_2[\mathbf{z}_{iq}] = p_1[\mathbf{z}_{iq}] \quad (\text{eq. 47})$$

After crossing, the mutation operator involves the modification of the value of 'gene' to maintain the genetic diversity from one generation of a population to the next. Mutation may be implemented by different methods: flip bit, random, boundary, uniform, non-uniform, or Gaussian. We have chosen here the Gaussian operator since it produced the best results for most fitness functions and gives good results [49, 50]. Essentially, this operator adds a unit Gaussian-distributed (with zero mean and unit variance) random value to the genes of each of the remaining $(N - (N_c + N_e))$ chromosomes. To implement the mutation, we add a random

number generated by a Gaussian distribution with zero mean to all positions of the genes in each selected chromosome. The new values of the genes, representing wavenumber positions in spectra, are then rounded to the nearest integer. The standard deviation of this distribution is the parameter that the call "scale" which is equal to 1 in the first generation, but this parameter is controlled during the next generations by another parameter which is "shrink". The standard deviation at the t^{th} generation, σ_t is the same at all coordinates of the parent chromosome, and is given by the recursive formula:

$$\sigma_t = \sigma_{t-1} \left(1 - \text{shrink} \frac{t}{T_{max}} \right) \quad (\text{eq. 48})$$

Where T_{max} is the numbers of generations. A low value of "shrink" produce a small decrease in the amplitude of the mutation on the indices of gene positions.

These different steps are repeated until one of the termination criteria is satisfied: the maximum number of iterations T_{max} has been reached or the weighted-average change in the fitness values over all generations is less than a tolerance ϵ .

4. Machine Learning

4.1 Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA)

Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) is a common technique used for dimensionality reduction and classification that has been extensively used for processing spectral information. Consider the classification problem of assigning a sample of observed variables extracted from the training set \mathbf{x}_j to the class c_k . The classification score is defined as

$$cf(\mathbf{x}_j) = (\mathbf{x}_j - \mu_k)^T \Sigma_k^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_j - \mu_k) + \ln|\Sigma_k| - 2 \ln[P(C = c_k)] \quad (\text{eq. 49})$$

where Σ_k is the class covariance matrix of class c_k , μ_k is the mean vector of class c_k , and $P(C = c_k)$ the prior probability of class c_k . They are estimated by:

$$\widehat{\mu}_k = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{j=1}^{n_k} \mathbf{x}_j \quad (\text{eq. 50})$$

$$\widehat{\Sigma}_k = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{j=1}^{n_k} (\mathbf{x}_j - \mu_k)(\mathbf{x}_j - \mu_k)^T \quad (\text{eq. 51})$$

$$P(\widehat{C} = c_k) = \frac{n_k}{n} \quad (\text{eq. 52})$$

where n_k is the number of samples in class c_k , and n is the total number of samples in the training dataset. The sample \mathbf{x}_j is assigned to the class for which it has the lowest classification score.

When the class covariance matrices are assumed to be equal, so that a pooled covariance matrix

$$\Sigma_{\text{pooled}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^K n_k \Sigma_k \quad (\text{eq.53})$$

is substituted for the class covariance matrix in (eq. 49). Ignoring constants, the following classification rule for LDA is derived

$$cf(\mathbf{x}_j) = (\mathbf{x}_j - \mu_k)^T \Sigma_{\text{pooled}}^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_j - \mu_k) - 2 \ln[P(C = c_k)] \quad (\text{eq. 54})$$

When the prior probability n_i is constant, eq. (54) corresponds to the Mahalanobis distance. The error rate R^{LDA} of the LDA classifier, which is defined as:

$$R^{LDA}(\mathbf{x}_j) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n |\text{sign}(c_k(\mathbf{x}_j) - \hat{c}_k(\mathbf{x}_j))|, \quad (\text{eq. 55})$$

with \mathbf{x}_j that belongs to the class c_k estimated by the LDA method classifier in the class \hat{c}_k .

4.2 Naive Bayesian classifier (NBC)

The naive Bayesian classifier is based on Bayes' theorem with independence assumptions between predictors. A naive Bayesian model is easy to build, with no complicated iterative parameter estimation which makes its short computational time for training [30]. Given $\mathbf{x}_j = [x_{j1}, \dots, x_{js}, \dots, x_{jS}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^S$, a sample of observed variables extracted from the training set \mathbf{X} belonging to a specific class c_k . The Naïve Bayes classifier will predict that \mathbf{x}_j belongs to the expected class \hat{C} having the Maximum a Posteriori Probability (MAP) conditioned on \mathbf{x}_j :

$$\text{MAP}(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j) = \arg \max_{k \in \{1, \dots, K\}} P(C = c_k | \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j). \quad (\text{eq. 56})$$

According to Bayes' theorem, the probability $P(C = c_k | \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j)$ that we want to compute can be expressed in terms of probabilities $P(C = c_k)$, $P(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j | C = c_k)$ and $P(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j)$ as:

$$P(C = c_k | \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j) = \frac{P(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j | C = c_k) P(C = c_k)}{P(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j)} \quad (\text{eq. 57})$$

where $P(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j)$ in the denominator can be ignored since it does not depend on C , and the value of $P(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j)$ is effectively known constant. $P(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j | C = c_k)$ is called the Class-conditional Probability Distribution (CPD). Thus, the calculation of the Naïve Bayes classifier is given by:

$$\text{MAP}(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j) = \arg \max_{k \in \{1, \dots, K\}} P(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j | C = c_k) P(C = c_k). \quad (\text{eq. 58})$$

The probability of a classification error, or the risk of the classifier, is defined as:

$$R^{NBC}(\mathbf{x}_j) = \sum_{\mathbf{x}_j \in \mathbf{X}} \mathbf{1}_{C(\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_j) \neq \hat{C}(\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_j)} P(\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}_j) = E_{\mathbf{X}} \left\{ \mathbf{1}_{C(\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_j) \neq \hat{C}(\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_j)} \right\} \quad (\text{eq. 59})$$

where $\mathbf{1}_{C(\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_j) \neq \widehat{C}(\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{x}_j)}$ is the indicator function and E_X is the expectation over X and $C(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j)$ is the true class which the vector \mathbf{x}_j belongs and $\widehat{C}(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x}_j)$ is the predicted class of \mathbf{x}_j given by the NBC algorithm. This misclassification rate is called the Bayes error (Bayes risk). The Bayes risk is the minimum misclassification rate when the distribution is known and is usually set as the benchmark when solving classification problems.

4.3 Multi-Class Support Vector Machine (SVM)

The support vector machines (SVMs) are a set of related learning algorithms used for classification and regression. SVM are non-parametric classifiers. The most basic scheme used for the implementation of SVM multi-class classification is the one-against-all method. In this simplest extension of the SVM to a K -class problem, K binary SVM models are constructed. In k^{th} class SVM problem, class c_k is separated from the remaining classes. All k binary SVM classifiers are combined together to make a final multi-class classifier. Here the remaining means that all the data points from classes other than c_k are combined to form one class c_l . The optimal hyperplane that separates data points from the class c_i and the combined class c_l is found by using the standard SVM approach. We denote the optimal separating hyperplane discriminating the class c_i and the combined class c_k as:

$$g_k(\mathbf{x}_j) = \mathbf{w}_k \cdot \varphi(\mathbf{x}_j) + \mathbf{b}_k \quad \mathbf{k} \in \{1, \dots, K\} \quad (\text{eq. 60})$$

where $\mathbf{w}_k \in \mathbb{R}^S$ is the weight vector, \mathbf{b} is the bias and the mapping function φ projects the training data into a suitable feature space \mathbb{R}^S to allow for nonlinear decision surfaces. The parameters of the decision function $g_k(\mathbf{x}_j)$ are determined by the following minimization:

$$\min J(\mathbf{w}_k, \xi) = \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{w}_k\|^2 + C \sum_{j=1}^n \xi_j \quad (\text{eq. 61})$$

subject to

$$y_j(\mathbf{w}_k^T \varphi(\mathbf{x}_j) + \mathbf{b}_k) \geq \mathbf{1} - \xi_j \quad \xi_j \geq \mathbf{0} ; j = 1 \dots n, \quad (\text{eq. 62})$$

with scalar $y_j \in \{-1, +1\}$ denoting its class label, $C \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is a regularization constant and ξ_j denote a slack variable can be introduced to relax the separability constraints in (eq. 61).

The decision rule $f_k(\mathbf{x}_j)$ that assigns the vector \mathbf{x}_j to the class c_k given by:

$$f_k(\mathbf{x}_j) = \text{sign}(g_i(\mathbf{x}_j)) \quad (\text{eq. 63})$$

The main difficulty in this approach is that the outputs of the classifiers $f_k(\mathbf{x}_j)$ are binary values. The usual way to handle this problem is to ignore the sign-operator in (eq. 63). After finding all the optimal hyperplanes given by $g_k(\mathbf{x}_j)$ for $\mathbf{k} \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, we say \mathbf{x}_j is in the class which has the largest value of the decision function and is given by:

$$\widehat{c}_k(\mathbf{x}_j) = \underset{k}{\operatorname{argmax}} g_k(\mathbf{x}_j) \quad (\text{eq. 64})$$

In this approach the index of the largest component of the discriminant functions $g_i(\mathbf{x}_j)$ for $\mathbf{k} \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ is assigned to the data point \mathbf{x}_j . The error rate R^{SVM} of the SVM classifier, which is defined as:

$$R^{SVM}(\mathbf{x}_j) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{1}_{c_k \neq \hat{c}_k}(\mathbf{x}_j), \quad (\text{eq. 65})$$

with \mathbf{x}_j that belongs to the class c_k estimated by the method classifier in the class \hat{c}_k and $\mathbf{1}_{c_k \neq \hat{c}_k}(\mathbf{x}_j)$ is the indicator function defined as:

$$\mathbf{1}_{c_k \neq \hat{c}_k}(\mathbf{x}_j) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if class } \hat{c}_k \text{ of } \mathbf{x}_j \neq \text{class } c_k, \\ 0 & \text{if class } \hat{c}_k \text{ of } \mathbf{x}_j = \text{class } c_k. \end{cases} \quad (\text{eq. 66})$$

4.4 Decision Tree Classifier (DTC)

A decision tree classifier is a non-parametric classifier that does not require any a priori statistical assumptions to be made regarding the distribution of data. The basic structure of the decision tree, however, consists of one root node, a number of internal nodes and finally a set of terminal nodes. A node is a subset of the predictors that is used to determine a split. A non-terminal node or parent node is a node that is further split into two child nodes. Growing a tree consists of selecting the optimal splits to determine a non-terminal node, and the assignment of each terminal node to a class. The data is recursively divided down the decision tree according to the defined classification framework.

Classes are simply assigned to a terminal node by observing which class is mostly commonly observed in that region of the tree. Thus, the challenge is to optimally choose the best variable and split that variable to maximize the purity or similarity among the responses. The impurity of a parent node τ , denoted $i(\tau)$, is zero when all observations are in the same class. A split s is determined by selecting the best predictor and split value that optimizes the highest reduction in purity:

$$\Delta(s, \tau) = i(\tau) - \sum_{b=1}^B p(\tau_b/\tau) i(\tau_b) \quad (\text{eq. 67})$$

where τ_b denotes child node b , $p(\tau_b/\tau)$ is the proportion of observations in τ that are assigned to τ_b , and B is the number of branches after splitting. Two common impurity functions are the entropy criterion:

$$i(\tau) = - \sum_{k=1}^K p_k \log_2(p_k) \quad (\text{eq. 68})$$

and the Gini index criterion

$$i(\tau) = - \sum_{k=1}^K p_k^2 \quad (\text{eq. 69})$$

where p_k is the proportion of observations in class c_k with $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$. Pruning is based upon successive steps of removing lower branches that lead to improved classification rates.

Once the final tree is determined by $\Delta(s, \tau)$, it is natural to evaluate its predictive performance by comparing the observed class to the predicted class from the CT for observation \mathbf{x}_j . In a terminal node m , representing a region R_m with n_m observations, let

$$\hat{p}_{mk} = \frac{1}{n_m} \sum_{j=1}^{n_m} \mathbf{1}_{c_k}(\mathbf{x}_j) \quad (\text{eq. 70})$$

denote the proportion of class c_k observations in terminal node m . We classify the observations in node m to class

$$\widehat{c}_k(\mathbf{x}_j) = \underset{k}{\operatorname{argmax}} \hat{p}_{mk} \quad (\text{eq. 71})$$

The misclassification error rate is simply the proportion of observations in the node that are not members of the majority class in that node.

$$R^{DTc}(\mathbf{x}_j) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(1 - \max_k(\hat{p}_{mk}(\mathbf{x}_j)) \right) \quad (\text{eq. 72})$$

5. Implementation of Metaheuristic Algorithms

The first step in our algorithm is to select relevant features from the original dataset by different metaheuristic algorithms combined with machine learning methods in which the error rate is used as the fitness function. Each combination is implemented several times until two consecutive implementations have the same fitness value. For all algorithms $T_{max} = 100$. The selected features are then used in the classification phase and classification accuracies are obtained.

The parameters chosen for the metaheuristic algorithms are as follows:

- BGWO: number of wolves (N) = 20.
- BPSO: number of particles (N) = 10, $c_1 = c_2 = 1$, $w = 0.9$.
- BCO: colony size (N) = 30, limit = 20.
- ACO: $\alpha = 0.5$, $\beta = 3$, $\tau_0 = 0.4$, $q_0 = 0.5$, $\rho = 0.5$ and number of ants (N) = 10.
- GSO: number of masses (N) = 10, $G_0 = 100$, $\nu = 20$, $\varepsilon = 10^{-6}$.
- GA: $FRAC_c = 0.8$, $N_e = 2$, $\varepsilon = 10^{-6}$, $L=19$, $N=500$.

To quantify our classification results for variable selection methods, we propose to apply Self-Organizing Map, which is one of the Neural Network Classification methods, on the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by the different combined metaheuristic-machine learning algorithms.

5.1. Self-Organizing Map (SOM)

Self-Organizing Map (SOM) is a type of neural network that is trained to produce a two-dimensional discretized representation of the input space of the training samples, called a map. Precisely, it is a nonlinear, ordered, smooth mapping of high-dimensional input data onto the elements of a regular, low-dimensional array. Because of their ability to convert the nonlinear statistical relationships between high-dimensional data into simple geometric relationship, the SOM maps can be used for classification and visualizing of data. SOM can be used either as a supervised or an unsupervised machine learning classification technique depending whether the labels (target variable) is available or not. In this work a 10×10 SOM Neural Network is used as a supervised classification algorithm since strawberry labels are available.

The SOM neural networks methodology enables us to design useful nonlinear systems accepting large numbers of inputs, with the design based solely on instances of input-output relationships (e.g., feature matrix $X(\mathbf{z}_{optimal})$ and pattern category \mathbf{c}_k , with $\mathbf{z}_{optimal}$ is the optimal solution selected by the different combined metaheuristic-machine learning algorithms. More details about the SOM Neural Network can be found in the **Appendix A** section.

5.2. Cross-Validation (CV)

Cross-validation is a model assessment technique used to evaluate a supervised classification algorithm's performance in making predictions on new datasets that it has not been trained on.

This is done by partitioning a dataset and using a subset to train the SOM neural networks algorithm and the remaining data for validation and testing. Several methods of cross validation exist such as k-fold, Holdout, Leave-out and Re-substitution. We use k-fold method that partitions spectra of strawberries into $k = 5$ randomly chosen subsets of roughly equal size. One subset is used to validate the model (1/5 of data = 89 spectra), one subset is used to test the model (1/5 of data = 89 spectra), training the model uses the remaining subsets (3/5 of data = 265 spectra). This process is repeated 100 times such that each subset is used exactly once for validation. The proposed methodology has been applied with four different fitness functions (LDA, NBC, SVM, DTC).

6. Strawberries Sector and Data Collection

6.1. General Overview

Agriculture in France is growing in a rapid pace especially with the introduction of modern technology and techniques. Many advanced devices are being implemented in the favor of developing agriculture industry. In a narrower scope, strawberries are considered among the basic meals in the French diet. In 2019, the production volume of strawberries in France was estimated to be 60,408 tons. For a better shelf life, the need to determine the time of harvesting strawberries crop has risen. Many factors influence strawberry maturity such as temperature, irrigation, fertilization, solar radiations, pesticides, type of soil, etc. So, it is important to know what are the most relevant factors affecting the growth and maturity of strawberries. For that, MIR-spectral data was extracted using friendly-nature advanced devices.

6.2. Data Set Collection

6.2.1. Data Set

In this section, we first present the strawberry maturity samples and the acquisition of MIR spectra using portable spectroscopy instruments. As infrared spectra must be pretreated before applying chemometric methods, preprocessing signal methods are next presented.

Strawberry fruit samples of three different greenhouses in north France during the 2017–2018 growing season were used in this analysis. The strawberries data set was composed of 443 samples with approximately the same number of samples for each of the eight the colorimetric maturity level: Green, White, Red 1/2, Red 1, Red 2, Red 4, Red 6, Red 8. Data distribution is presented in **Figure16** .

Figure16 : Data distribution among the 8 maturity classes of strawberries

Experts in the field classified the samples in these classes using a colorimetric maturity scale code intended for experimenters or breeders to characterize the color of strawberry varieties. The scale code shown in **Figure17** includes several shades with and without achenes, as well as a calibration plate.

Figure17 : The colorimetric maturity scale used to class the strawberry fruits

6.2.2. Spectral acquisition and pre-processing

MIR spectra were collected in situ directly on the strawberries with an Agilent 4300 FTIR - IR spectrometer equipped with an ATR diamond sample interface. The ATR (attenuated total reflectance) is a surface technique and only the upper 2-3 microns are analyzed. This accessory is mainly used for the analysis of solids, liquids, pastes and gels. All the spectra were acquired with a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Before each acquisition, a reference spectrum of the atmospheric environment was recorded with several accumulations, and it was then subtracted from each recorded spectrum. The MIR wavenumber region chosen was 500 – 4000 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the principal vibrations of chemical functional groups associated to fruits. A data instance (e.g., a MIR spectra of all strawberry fruit samples) is characterized by a number of independent variables (features) e.g., the wavenumber range of Mid-infrared. It may also have a response variable (often called a label), e.g., the colorimetric maturity level.

All spectra were preprocessed with an Extended Multiplicative Signal Correction (EMSC) preprocessing method. In addition, we have tested several pre-treatment methods such as, standard normal variate (SNV), baseline removal (LB) with different polynomial orders, LB followed by SNV, multiplicative scatter correction, extended multiplicative scatter correction, first- and second-order Savitzky-Golay derivation (SG) with smoothing with different window sizes points and polynomial orders followed by SNV. The best results were obtained by with the EMSC preprocessing method. This preprocessing was found as being efficient for discriminating strawberries samples by classifying MIR spectra. The preprocessed MIR spectra with EMSC are illustrated in **Figure 18**.

Figure 18: MIR spectra of all samples covering the wavenumber range from 500 to 4000 cm⁻¹ after their pre-processing by EMSC.

The metaheuristic algorithms didn't face any problem with the balance of the data or the dimensionality of each class. All classification accuracies and features selected were obtained using MATLAB R2021a software installed on an Intel(R) Core (TM) i5 CPU @ 3.20GHz x64-bit processor with 4 GB RAM computer.

The data was split onto many levels of cross-validation respectively: 80% training set, 10% validation set, & 10% test set, 70-15-15, 60-20-20, and 50-25-25. In this thesis we are mostly interested in the 60-20-20 formation.

7. Results of Metaheuristic Algorithm's application to MIR - spectra strawberry dataset

The figures listed below are computed on MATLAB using the Confusion Matrix and the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve.

A confusion matrix is used to describe the performance of a classification model on a set of test data for which the true values are known. It is a summary of prediction results on a classification problem and allows the visualization of the performance of an algorithm. Hence, the elements in the diagonal are the elements correctly classified, while the elements out of the diagonal are misclassified. It can easily be seen that the overall accuracy can be computed by dividing the sum of the diagonal elements (number of correctly classified samples) by the total sum of the elements of the matrix (total number of samples in the dataset).

A ROC curve summarizes the performance of a classifier over all possible thresholds. It is generated by plotting the True Positive Rate (y-axis) against the False Positive Rate (x-axis) by

varying the threshold for assigning observations to a given class. A ROC curve is a performance measurement for classification problem at various thresholds settings. The plot of True Positive Rate (TPR; sensitivity) versus False Positive Rate (FPR; 1-specificity) across varying cut-offs generates a curve in the unit square called a ROC curve. ROC curves are used to compare different supervised classifiers. In our case we have used to compare the same supervised classification algorithm, SOM but using the wavenumbers extracted by the combination of metaheuristic algorithms and machine learning methods. If the curve has high values, it leads to the greater of area under the curve obtained, and the less error the classifier makes. ROC curve corresponding to progressively greater discriminant capacity are located progressively closer to the upper left-hand corner in "ROC space". Sensitivity (Se) and Specificity (Sp) are more illustrated in the **Appendix B** section.

7.1. Feature Selection Results

In terms of selecting relevant and important features, the performance of GA surpasses other metaheuristics in 3 out of 4 of the cases (GA-LDA, GA-NBC, GA-SVM) and selected the minimum number of features and reached to 18 out of 900 wavenumbers available.

Figure 19: Number of features selected by Metaheuristic algorithms

Figure 19 illustrates that GA is the most robust feature selection method followed by BPSO, BGWO, ACO, BCO, and GSO ranked from best to worst. BGWO, BPSO, and ACO have approximately a similar behavior in selecting features, while BCO and GSO failed to reduce

the number of features below 150. Moving to the ML approach, we can notice that in 3 out of 6 cases, metaheuristics combined with DTC has the best results among ML methods, whereas also in 3 out of 6 cases, metaheuristics combined with SVM has the second-best results among ML methods. The minimum number of features selected is 13 by BPSO-DTC and the greatest number of features selected is 191 by GSO-NBC. **Figure 19** also indicates that within the same metaheuristic, there no big difference between the number of features selected by ML methods. The maximum difference is 29 (ACO), whereas the minimum difference is 0 (GA).

Figure20 : Minimum fitness values obtained by metaheuristic algorithms

Figure20 reveals that SVM and LDA combined to metaheuristics have relatively same behavior and equal fitness values. BCO-LDA, GSO-LDA, and GA-LDA can be classified as low fitness value algorithms, while BPSO-LDA, BGWO-LDA, ACO-LDA can be classified as high fitness value algorithms. At a wider scope, SVM combined to metaheuristics have better fitness values than other ML methods in 4 out of 6 cases. Moving to metaheuristic comparison, BCO obtained the best fitness values in 3 out of 4 cases. GSO obtained the second minimum fitness values in 2 cases out of 4 (GSO-LDA, GSO-SVM). When controlling on LDA, BCO obtained the best result (0.0303). When controlling on NBC, BCO, ACO, and BPSO obtained the best results of (0.0833). When controlling on SVM, BCO and GSO obtained the best results (0.0277) and they

are the best global fitness attained by all algorithms. When controlling on DTC, GA obtained the best result (0.1). The highest fitness value obtained is for BSO-DTC (0.1515).

7.2. Analysis of discrimination of samples during the maturity process

Each figure shows the confusion matrix for the true labels targets and predicted labels outputs. The rows correspond to the predicted class (Output Class) extract by classification methods and the columns correspond to the strawberry maturity true class (Target Class). The diagonal cells correspond to spectra that are correctly classified. The off-diagonal cells correspond to incorrectly classified spectra of maturity of strawberries. The results of SOM Neural Network classification accuracy registered the following:

Out of all the combinations of algorithms, the GA-LDA is the most robust combination among them all, with the best results reached over an 80-10-10 cross-validation. Whereas DTC shows the lowest accuracies indicating weak classification abilities.

In this part we are interested only in the 60%/20%/20% split as it represents an ideal distribution of the data.

Table1 : Results of SOM Neural Network Classification for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by: (A) GA-LDA, (B) GA- NBC, (C) GA-SVM, and (D) GA-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

A

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix									(b) Validation Confusion Matrix									(c) Test Confusion Matrix									
		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8		
Output Class	Red 8	20 7.5%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%	9 10.1%	0	1 1.1%	0	0	0	0	0	90.0%	5 5.6%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%	
	Red 6	0	16 6.0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%	0	6 6.7%	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%	0	11 12.4%	1 1.1%	0	0	0	0	0	91.7%	
	Red 4	0	0	44 16.6%	0	0	0	0	0	100%	0	0	7 7.9%	0	0	0	0	0	100%	0	1	14 15.7%	0	0	0	0	1	87.5%	
	Red 2	0	0	0	45 17.0%	0	0	0	0	100%	0	0	0	15 16.9%	1 1.1%	0	0	0	93.8%	0	0	0	7 7.9%	0	0	0	0	100%	
	Red 1	0	0	0	0	21 7.9%	0	0	0	100%	0	0	0	0	10 11.2%	0	0	0	100%	0	0	0	0	10 11.2%	0	0	0	100%	
	Red ½	0	0	0	0	0	50 18.9%	0	0	100%	0	0	0	0	0	16 18.0%	0	0	100%	0	0	0	0	0	12 13.5%	0	0	100%	
	White	0	0	0	0	0	0	47 17.7%	0	100%	1 1.1%	0	0	0	0	0	15 16.9%	0	93.8%	1 1.1%	0	0	0	0	0	0	14 15.7%	1 1.1%	87.5%
	Green	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22 8.3%	100%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8 9.0%	100%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11 12.4%	100%
		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	90.0%	100%	87.5%	100%	90.9%	100%	100%	100%	96.6%	83.3%	91.7%	93.3%	100%	100%	100%	100%	84.6%	94.4%	
		0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	10.0%	0.0%	12.5%	0.0%	9.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	3.4%	16.7%	8.3%	6.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	15.4%	5.6%	

B

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix								(b) Validation Confusion Matrix								(c) Test Confusion Matrix								
Output Class	Green	White	Red ½	Red ¼	Green	White	Red ½	Red ¼	Green	White	Red ½	Red ¼														
	Green	23	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0
	White	0	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
	Red ½	0	0	41	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	14	0	0	0	0	1
	Red ¼	0	0	0	15.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	7.9%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	1	1	0	0	0	1	19	0	1	0	0	0
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	0	26	0	0	0	0	0	2	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	5	0	0	0
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	0	0	49	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	1	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	1	0
	Red ¼	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	40	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	1	1	0	0	0	14	0	0	0
Red ¼	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	27	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	
Red ¼	95.8%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	93.0%	100%	98.5%	100%	100%	77.8%	88.2%	90.9%	93.6%	93.6%	80.0%	89.9%	60.0%	83.3%	82.4%	95.0%	100%	92.3%	82.4%	83.3%
Red ¼	4.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	7.0%	0.0%	1.5%	0.0%	0.0%	22.2%	11.8%	9.1%	6.2%	6.2%	20.0%	10.1%	40.0%	16.7%	17.6%	5.0%	0.0%	7.7%	17.6%	16.7%

C

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix								(b) Validation Confusion Matrix								(c) Test Confusion Matrix								
Output Class	Green	White	Red ½	Red ¼	Green	White	Red ½	Red ¼	Green	White	Red ½	Red ¼														
	Green	15	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
	White	0	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
	Red ½	0	0	47	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	8	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Red ¼	0	0	0	17.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	3.4%	12.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	43	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	1	2	0	0	0
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	0	31	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	7	0	0	0
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	0	0	11.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.1%	3.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	7.9%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	2
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	43	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	0	0
Red ¼	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	41	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	3	7	0	
Red ¼	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	25	4	0	1	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	10	0	0	
Red ¼	93.8%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	95.3%	100%	98.9%	69.2%	70.0%	91.7%	92.3%	100%	93.3%	94.2%	100%	85.4%	85.7%	71.4%	100%	87.5%	95.0%	100%	71.4%	
Red ¼	6.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	4.7%	0.0%	1.1%	30.8%	30.0%	8.3%	7.7%	0.0%	6.7%	15.8%	0.0%	14.6%	14.3%	28.6%	0.0%	18.2%	12.5%	15.0%	0.0%	28.6%

D

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix								(b) Validation Confusion Matrix								(c) Test Confusion Matrix								
Output Class	Green	White	Red ½	Red ¼	Green	White	Red ½	Red ¼	Green	White	Red ½	Red ¼														
	Green	25	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
	White	0	19	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Red ½	0	0	4	38	0	0	0	0	0	1	8	0	0	0	0	0	1	13	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	15.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.1%	1.1%	9.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	14.6%	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	13.3%
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	0	0	49	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	38	1	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0
	Red ¼	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	1	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0
Red ¼	100%	79.2%	97.4%	100%	100%	100%	95.0%	92.3%	71.4%	75.0%	66.7%	100%	90.0%	100%	88.9%	88.9%	87.6%	100%	83.3%	81.2%	88.9%	91.7%	93.8%	77.8%	100%	
Red ¼	0.0%	20.8%	2.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	5.0%	7.7%	28.6%	25.0%	33.3%	0.0%	10.0%	0.0%	11.1%	11.1%	12.4%	0.0%	16.7%	18.8%	11.1%	8.3%	6.2%	22.2%	0.0%	

The results of SOM Neural Network classification accuracy registered 100% of training datasets, 96.6% of validation datasets and 94.4% of test datasets for the newly correlated variables selected by GA-LDA describing a maturity index. However, the classification accuracy is less good for the GA-NBC algorithm with 98.5% of training datasets, 89.9% of

validation datasets and 86.5% of test datasets correctly classified, the GA-SVM algorithm with 98.9% of training datasets, 85.4% of validation datasets and 85.4% of test datasets correctly classified and GA-DTC algorithm with 96.2% of training datasets, 87.6% of validation datasets and 87.6% of test datasets correctly classified. These values, presented in Table1 confirm that the GA-LDA algorithm allows a better discriminate within the state of maturity process than state of art methods that take into consideration the wavenumbers selected by the, GA-NBC, GA-SVM, GA-DTC.

Table 2: Results of SOM Neural Network Classification for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by: (A) BCO-LDA, (B) BCO-NBC, (C) BCO-SVM, and (D) BCO-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

The results of SOM Neural Network classification accuracy registered 100 % of training datasets, 91% of validation datasets and 85.4% of test datasets for the newly correlated variables selected by BCO-LDA describing a maturity index. However, the classification accuracy is less good for the BCO-NBC algorithm with 100% of training datasets, 88.8% of validation datasets and 88.8% of test datasets correctly classified, the BCO-SVM algorithm with 99.2% of training datasets, 80.9% of validation datasets and 92.1% of test datasets correctly classified and BCO-DTC algorithm with 100% of training datasets, 89.9% of validation datasets and 93.3% of test datasets correctly classified. These values, presented in Table 2, confirm that the BCO-DTC algorithm allows a better discriminate within the state of maturity process than state of art methods that take into consideration the wavenumbers selected by the, BCO-NBC, BCO-SVM, BCO-LDA.

Table 3 : Results of SOM Neural Network Classification for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by: (A) GSO-LDA, (B) GSO-NBC, (C) GSO-SVM, and (D) GSO-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

A

B

C

D

The results of SOM Neural Network classification accuracy registered 100 % of training datasets, 92.1% of validation datasets and 89.9% of test datasets for the newly correlated variables selected by GSO-LDA describing a maturity index. However, the classification accuracy is less good for the GSO-NBC algorithm with 98.5% of training datasets, 83.1% of validation datasets and 88.8% of test datasets correctly classified, the GSO-SVM algorithm with 100% of training datasets, 89.9% of validation datasets and 91% of test datasets correctly classified and GSO-DTC algorithm with 99.2% of training datasets, 86.5% of validation datasets and 83.1% of test datasets correctly classified. These values, presented in **Table 3**, confirm that the GSO-LDA and GSO-SVM algorithms allow a better discriminate within the state of maturity process than state of art methods that take into consideration the wavenumbers selected by the, GSO-NBC and GSO-DTC.

Table 4: Results of SOM Neural Network Classification for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at all wavenumbers shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra)

The results of SOM Neural Network classification accuracy registered 42.3% of training dataset, 30.3% of validation dataset and 31.5% of test dataset of the 900 original features. It is obvious that without the use of feature selection methods, classification abilities are very weak.

A

B

C

D

Figure 21: ROC curve of SOM Neural Network classifier for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by genetic algorithms (A) GA-LDA, (B) GA-NBC, (C) GA-SVM, and (D) GA-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

Figure 21 represents the comparisons between ROC curves using the SOM with the wavebands extracted by GA-LDA, GA-NBC, GA-SVM and GA-DTC for each class of state of maturity process of strawberries. Each figure is broken down into three graphs of Training ROC (applied on 60% of spectra), Validation ROC (applied on 20% of spectra), (c) Test ROC (applied on 20% of spectra). We can see that the classification threshold in the GA-LDA method is very close to 1 and very far from diagonal for all the classes of strawberry maturity process compared to other methods. But the classification threshold is considerably reduced for the GA-SVM method and relatively reduced for the GA-DTC method. This result shows the GA fitness function based on LDA allows to identify for our application wavenumbers allowing to perform a better discrimination within the maturity than the GA fitness functions based on NBC, SVM and DTC methods. The area under the curves of each class of strawberry maturity for the GA-LDA method is higher than that for GA-NBC, GA-SVM and GA-DTC methods. This also confirms that the measures of sensitivity and specificity of ROC curves for LDA algorithm are generally stronger than the other ROC curves for GA-NBC, GA-SVM and GA-DTC algorithms for each class of state of maturity process of strawberry in all Figure 21(A-D), which indicates better in-sample accuracy than the other classifier methods. Furthermore, the GA-LDA model was significantly different to all of the other models except the GA-NBC model.

A

Figure 22: ROC curve of SOM Neural Network classifier for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by genetic algorithms (A) BCO-LDA, (B) BCO-NBC, (C) BCO-SVM, and (D) BCO-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

Figure 22 represents the comparisons between ROC curves using the SOM with the wavebands extracted by BCO-LDA, BCO-NBC, BCO-SVM and BCO-DTC for each class of state of maturity process of strawberries. Each figure is broken down into three graphs of Training ROC (applied on 60% of spectra), Validation ROC (applied on 20% of spectra), (c) Test ROC (applied on 20% of spectra). We can see that the classification threshold in the BCO-LDA, BCO-SVM, and BCO-DTC methods are very close to 1 and very far from diagonal for most of the classes of strawberry maturity process compared to other methods. But the classification

threshold is considerably reduced for the BCO-NBC. This result shows the BCO fitness function based on most ML methods allows to identify for our application relevant wavenumbers. The area under the curves of each class of strawberry maturity for the BCO-LDA, BCO-SVM, and BCO-DTC methods is higher than that for BCO-NBC method. This also confirms that the measures of sensitivity and specificity of ROC curves for the three algorithms are generally stronger than the other ROC curves for BCO-NBC algorithm for each class of state of maturity process of strawberry in all **Figure 22(A-D)**, which indicates better in-sample accuracy than the other classifier method. Furthermore, the GA-LDA model was significantly different to all of the other models whereas BCO-SVM and BCP-NBC have approximately similar behaviors.

D

Figure 23: ROC curve of SOM Neural Network classifier for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by genetic algorithms (A) GSO-LDA, (B) GSO-NBC, (C) GSO-SVM, and (D) GSO-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

Figure 23 represents the comparisons between ROC curves using the SOM with the wavebands extracted by GSO-LDA, GSO-NBC, GSO-SVM and GSO-DTC for each class of state of maturity process of strawberries. Each figure is broken down into three graphs of Training ROC (applied on 60% of spectra), Validation ROC (applied on 20% of spectra), (c) Test ROC (applied on 20% of spectra). We can see that the classification threshold in the GSO-LDA method is very close to 1 and very far from diagonal for all the classes of strawberry maturity process except for class Red 4 compared to other methods. But the classification threshold is considerably reduced for the GSO-SVM method and relatively reduced for the GSO-DTC method. This result shows the GSO fitness function based on LDA allows to identify for our application wavenumbers allowing to perform a better discrimination within the maturity than the GA fitness functions based on NBC, SVM and DTC methods. The area under the curves of each class of strawberry maturity for the GSO-LDA method is higher than that for GSO-NBC, GSO-SVM and GSO-DTC methods. This also confirms that the measures of sensitivity and specificity of ROC curves for LDA algorithm are generally stronger than the other ROC curves for GSO-NBC, GSO-SVM and GSO-DTC algorithms for each class of state of maturity process of strawberry in all Figure 23(A-D), which indicates better in-sample accuracy than the other classifier methods. Furthermore, the GSO-LDA model was significantly different to all of the other models.

Figure 24: ROC curve of SOM Neural Network classifier for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at all wavenumbers shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

Figure 24 represents the ROC curves using the SOM with the original 900 wavebands. The figure is broken down into three graphs of Training ROC (applied on 60% of spectra), Validation ROC (applied on 20% of spectra), (c) Test ROC (applied on 20% of spectra). We can see that all classification thresholds are very far from 1 and very close from diagonal for all the classes of strawberry maturity process. The area under the curves of each class of strawberry maturity are very small which indicates that the original dataset of features is invalid for classification purposes. This also confirms that the measures of sensitivity and specificity of ROC curves are very weak. Moreover, the graphs for classes Red 1, Red 2, and Green go below the diagonal for some values of TPR and FPR, which indicates lack of classification abilities.

The results of confusion matrices and ROC curves for BGWO, BPSO, and ACO are presented in the **Appendix C** section.

7.3. Effect of the pre-processing method of spectra

The pre-processing of spectra is an important step that might influence the final result. We have tested the commonly used methods in agricultural and biological applications: Savitzky-Golay (SG) derivation of order 1 and 2 followed by SNV, Multiplicative Scatter Correction (MSC), and Extended Multiplicative Scatter Correction (EMSC). **Table 5** shows the of percentages of good classification of LDA, NBC, SVM and DTC supervised algorithms applied on all spectral range of wavenumbers of spectra of strawberries pretreated by different preprocessing methods. These values confirm that the EMSC is the best preprocessing method for different methods of supervised classifications.

Table 5: Values of the percentages of classification of LDA, NBC, SVM and DTC algorithms for spectra pretreated by commonly pre-processing methods.

	LDA	NBC	SVM	DTC
SG2-SNV	82%	79%	57%	72%
SG1-SNV	87%	82%	55%	76%
MSC	88%	61%	52%	71%
EMSC	100%	100%	95%	98%

7.4. Effect of cross-validation sampling technique

Cross validation is the most important part of machine learning models and the results might depend on it. We have tested here the SOM Neural Network classification on the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by the proposed algorithms on different size of testing, validation and training datasets.

To compare the influence of the validation part, we have computed the accuracy of SOM-NN classification on MIR spectra at the wavenumbers selected by each method of the variable selection algorithm. The values, shown in figures **Figure25 -Figure 28**, indicate that GA-LDA gives the best results in classification in 3 out of 4 splits (25%, 15%, 10% test sets) while BGWO-SVM gives the best result in the 20% test set split (95.5%). The worst accuracy attained is for GA-SVM (68.9%) from the 50%/25%/25% split, whereas the best accuracy attained is for GA-LDA (99%) from the 80%/10%/10% split.

Figure25 : Discriminatory accuracy performance of proposed algorithms for 25% test set

Figure25 shows the results of the 50%/25%/25% split. There is no clear pattern about the accuracy behavior between the metaheuristic algorithms. The most noticeable remark is that in general ACO has the worst performances while BCO has high performances. GSO, BGWO, BPSO have relatively average performances. As for the GA, when combined with LDA and NBC it gives very high accuracies (94.6%, 91.4% respectively) while when combined with SVM and DTC it attains low accuracies (68.9%, 78.4% respectively).

Figure26 : Discriminatory accuracy performance of proposed algorithms for 20% test set

Figure26 shows the results of the 60%/20%/20% split. Similar to the 50%/25%/25% split the current split has no clear patterns for the accuracies. In general, BCO is the most robust algorithm combined with different ML methods. GSO and GA have approximately similar performances, while the weakest algorithm is BPSO. Unexpectedly BGWO-SVM surpasses any other combination of algorithms and reached an accuracy of 95.5%.

Figure 27: Discriminatory accuracy performance of proposed algorithms for 15% test set

Figure 27 shows the results of the 70%/15%/15% split. We can notice that most algorithms have high performances except for BGWO-NBC (72.7%), BPSO-NBC (75.8%), ACO-LDA (77.3%), ACO-NBC (78.8%). Out of 4 worst accuracies, NBC has the share of 3. GA surpasses the other five algorithms in 2 cases (LDA, NBC). For the GSO 3 out of 4 accuracies are above 90%.

Figure 28: Discriminatory accuracy performance of proposed algorithms for 10% test set

Figure 28 shows the results of the 80%/10%/10% split. The results indicate that GSO, BCO, and GA belong to the high accuracy class, while BPSO and BGWO belong to the medium accuracy class. ACO performs well when combined with SVM and DTC only. The most robust algorithm is GSO having all 4 accuracies above 90%, whereas the weakest algorithm is the ACO having 2 out of 4 accuracies below 80%.

It is good to mention that for some algorithms (BCO, GSO, GA), as the training set size increases, the accuracies across the ML methods also increases.

8. Discussion

As we just witnessed, some algorithms are able to reduce large dimensional spaces into less than 20 dimensions where others were stuck in 150 features and above. This is due to the nature and mechanism of the algorithms used. BGWO, BPSO, ACO, GA are robust dimensional reduction algorithms while BCO and GSO fail to reduce a 900-dimensional space efficiently. Despite the previous results the latter algorithms attained fitness values better than the BGWO, BPSO, ACO, GA.

Moving to the accuracy part, it is proven that GA surpasses in most cases (3 out of 4 CV divisions) the other five algorithms. This is due to the variety of stages that this algorithm goes through, like crossover and mutation processes. BGWO-SVM proved its high ability and robustness in the 60-20-20 division and this is due to the wolves ranking property which declares alpha wolves as the best solution, beta wolves as the second-best solution and gamma wolves as the third best solution.

In the literature, numerous MIR spectral-categorization techniques were designed over the years to increase the ability of distinguishing among several strawberry and other fruits maturity processes; namely the Metaheuristic-based methods.

The manual extraction of features is in the ML techniques, succeeded by a feature classification. This procedure which is applied by many researchers, is time-consuming and monotonous. GA and five other metaheuristics were used to reduce dataset dimensionality and classify the MIR spectral data.

In this work, metaheuristic-ML methods are implemented in the purpose of comparing their performances in reducing dimensionality in addition to correct classification abilities. Moreover, our work relied on ROC curves to evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithms. In this thesis, the confusion matrix was used to test the accuracy. Besides, Cross-validation is the most popular method to evaluate the performance of the models; hence, we evaluated our models on four different cross-validations and then chose the best accuracy at 80% training test, 10% validation set, and 10% test set obtained by GA-LDA.

Former studies worked on only using one type of ML method. Our study overcomes the past ones by not only comparing metaheuristics performances but also implementing different ML methods as fitness functions, which is so far a one-of-a-kind trial. Furthermore, our study reached valid results with around 95.5% classification accuracy with BGWO-SVM in the 20% test division.

In the present study, the main goal was to bring into play the most popular and trained metaheuristics. Then, many cross-validation levels were implemented in order to decide on the leading one for the data, by avoiding any over-fitting problems. Finally, yet importantly, the selection of the best combination, resulting in the highest efficiency rates. Accordingly, the choice of the GA implementation with the LDA classifier at the 80-10-10 cross-validation level was a cut above the rest.

9. Conclusion

This study has demonstrated the potential of metaheuristic algorithms as band selectors using mid infrared spectra to differentiate between the eight states of maturity of strawberry. Our results demonstrated that strawberry maturity indices could be robustly quantified, precisely classified and empirically ordered using mid-infrared spectroscopy and machine learning analyzes. We have generated several methodologies based on the combination of variable selection and supervised learning. We tested the proposed metaheuristic algorithms which are BGWO-NBC, BGWO-DTC, BGWO-LDA, BGWO-SVM, BPSO-NBC, BPSO-DTC, BPSO-LDA, BPSO-SVM, BCO-NBC, BCO-DTC, BCO-LDA, BCO-SVM, GA-NBC, GA-DTC, GA-LDA, GA-SVM, ACO-NBC, ACO-DTC, ACO-LDA, ACO-SVM, GSO-NBC, GSO-DTC, GSO-LDA, GSO-SVM.

The ability of different algorithms is confirmed to best detect the ripeness of the strawberry. The results of our method prove that GA-LDA and BGWO-SVM allow better discrimination within the maturity process than advanced methods which take into account the number of waves selected by other metaheuristic-ML methods. The application of the GA and BGWO allows the identification of the wavenumbers that best highlight the discrimination within the of maturity of strawberries. The methods and approaches we have applied to strawberries should apply to other fruits, vegetables and special crops.

Further studies should be performed to investigate some issues, for example, a study that takes into account a priori information such as the maturity process into the objective function or concentrations through partial least square models. Furthermore, it would be very interesting to apply of new technology in the search for the process of maturation of strawberries such as the deep learning technique which allows to extract the spectral features to classify the state of maturity of strawberry. Also, it would be beneficial to implement other metaheuristics like Whale optimization, Bat algorithm, Simulated Annealing, etc.

Appendix A

Self-Organizing Map (SOM)

Self Organizing Maps (SOM) or Kohonen's map is a type of artificial neural network introduced by Teuvo Kohonen in the 1980s.

A SOM is an unsupervised learning algorithm trained using dimensionality reduction (typically two-dimensional), discretized representation of input space of the training samples, called a map. It differs from other Artificial Neural Network (ANN) as they apply competitive learning and not the error-correction learning (like backpropagation with gradient descent). They use a neighborhood function to preserve the topological properties of the input space to reduce data by creating a spatially organized representation, and also helps to discover the correlation between data.

Although SOM has been initially proposed for data visualization, it has been applied to different problems, including a solution to the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP).

Applications:

Dimensionality reduction and data visualization: In terms of dimensionality reduction, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is actually one of the most popular tools and has been broadly used. Compared to PCA, SOM has an advantage in maintaining the topological (structural) information of the training data and is not inherently linear. Using PCA on high-dimensional data may cause a loss of data when the dimension is reduced to two. If the target data has a lot of dimensions and every dimension is equally essential, SOM can be very useful over PCA.

Seismic facies analysis for oil and gas exploration: Seismic facies analysis refers to the interpretation of facies type from the seismic reflector information. It generates groups based on the identification of different individual features. These methods find an organization in the dataset and form organized relational clusters. However, these clusters may or may not have any physical analogs. A calibration method to relate SOM clusters to physical reality is needed. This calibration method must define the mapping between the groups and the measured physical properties; it should also provide an estimate of the validity of the relationships.

Text Clustering: Text clustering is an unsupervised learning process, i.e., not dependent on the prior knowledge of data, and based solely on the similarity relationship between documents in the collection to separate the document collection into some clusters. Text clustering's important preprocessing step is to check how the text can be shown in the form of the mathematical expression for further analysis and processing. The Common method is Salton's vector space model (Vector Space Model (VSM)).

Self Organizing Maps architecture:

Self-organizing maps consist of two layers, the first one is the input layer, and the second one is the output layer, also called a feature map.

SOM can integrate multi-modal input vectors and can extract relations among them in a 2-dimensional plane. SOM can also be used for the clustering of unlabeled data or classify labeled data with labeling the output units after learning. Unlike other ANN types, SOM doesn't have activation functions in neurons, and we directly pass weights to the output layer without doing anything.

Figure29 : Dimensionality Reduction in SOM-NN

Each data point in the data set competes to get recognition for representation. SOM mapping steps start from initializing the weight vectors. From there, a sample vector is selected randomly, and the map of the weight vectors is searched to find the weight which can best represent that sample. Each weight vector maintains neighboring weights that are close to it. The weight that is selected is rewarded by being able to become more like that randomly selected sample vector. The neighbors of that weight are also considered by being able to become more like the selected sample vector. This allows the map to form different shapes. Most generally, they have square/rectangular/hexagonal/L shapes in the 2D feature space.

The Algorithm:

The learning procedure of a SOM is described below.

1. Let $W_{ij}(t)$ be the weight from an input layer unit i to a Kohonen layer unit j at time t . W_{ij} is initialized using random numbers.

2. Let $X_i(t)$ be the data input to the input layer unit i at time t ; calculate the Euclidean distance d_j between $X_i(t)$ and $W_{ij}(t)$

3. Search for a Kohonen layer unit to minimize d_j , which is designated as the best matching unit.

4. Update the weight $W_{ij}(t)$ of a Kohonen layer unit contained in the neighborhood region of the best matching unit $N_c(t)$ using (2), where $\alpha(t)$ is a learning coefficient.

$$W_{ij}(t + 1) = W_{ij}(t) + \alpha(t) (X_i(t) - W_{ij}(t)) \quad (\text{eq. 73})$$

5. Repeat processes 2–4 up to the maximum iteration of learning.

Best Matching Unit is a technique which calculates the distance from each weight to the sample vector, by running through the entire set.

Appendix B

In literature, there are lots of evaluation metrics that have been used to investigate the performance an algorithm or model. The most popular evaluation metrics are reviewed and presented as follows:

True positive (TP): The actual observations are from positive class and are estimated to be positive.

True negative (TN): The actual observations are from negative class and are estimated by the model to be negative.

False positive (FP): When the model incorrectly estimates observations in the positive class.

False negative (FN): When the model incorrectly estimates the observations in the negative class.

Sensitivity/ True positive rate (TPR): It is the ration of observations that are true positive and the total number of observations that are actually positive i.e.,

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (\text{eq. 74})$$

Specificity / True Negative rate (TNR): It is the ration of the observations that are true negative and the total number of observations that are actually negative i.e.,

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \quad (\text{eq. 75})$$

Appendix C

All results are for 60%/20%/20% split.

1. Confusion matrices:

a. BGWO:

Table 6: Results of SOM Neural Network Classification for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by: (A) BGWO-LDA, (B) BGWO-NBC, (C) BGWO-SVM, and (D) BGWO-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

A

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix								(b) Validation Confusion Matrix								(c) Test Confusion Matrix							
		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8
Output Class	Green	17 6.4%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 0.4%	0 0.0%	5 5.6%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 1.1%	0 0.0%	1 1.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 1.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%
	White	0 0.0%	17 6.4%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 0.4%	0 0.0%	5 5.6%	1 1.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	5 5.6%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	4 4.5%
	Red ½	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	42 15.8%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	7 7.9%	13 14.6%	1 1.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	4 4.5%	12 13.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%
	Red 1	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	33 12.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	8 9.0%	2 2.2%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 1.1%	9 10.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%
	Red 2	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	31 11.7%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 2.2%	4 4.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	10 11.2%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%
	Red 4	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	51 19.2%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	9 10.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	11 12.4%	0 0.0%	1 1.1%	0 0.0%
	Red 6	2 0.8%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	40 15.1%	0 0.0%	3 3.4%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	20 22.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	4 4.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	17 19.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	
	Red 8	1 0.4%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 0.4%	28 10.6%	1 1.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	7 7.9%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 2.2%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 1.1%	6 6.7%	0 0.0%	
Target Class	95.0%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	95.2%	55.6%	41.7%	92.9%	72.7%	66.7%	100%	95.2%	100%	14.3%	55.6%	92.3%	100%	100%	89.5%	54.5%	79.8%		
15.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	4.8%	3.4%	2.3%	44.4%	58.3%	7.1%	27.3%	33.3%	0.0%	4.8%	0.0%	85.7%	44.4%	7.7%	0.0%	0.0%	10.5%	45.5%	20.2%		

B

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix								(b) Validation Confusion Matrix								(c) Test Confusion Matrix							
		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8
Output Class	Green	16 6.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	6 6.7%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 2.2%	0 0.0%	5 5.6%	0 0.0%	2 2.2%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	
	White	0 0.0%	22 8.3%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	6 6.7%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 1.1%	0 0.0%	5 5.6%	3 3.4%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 1.1%	
	Red ½	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	36 13.6%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 1.1%	10 11.2%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	15 16.9%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	
	Red 1	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	39 14.7%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	12 13.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	12 13.5%	3 3.4%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	
	Red 2	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	28 10.6%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 2.2%	3 3.4%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 2.2%	8 9.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	
	Red 4	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	47 17.7%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	17 19.1%	1 1.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	14 15.7%	0 0.0%	1 1.1%	0 0.0%	
	Red 6	1 0.4%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	47 17.7%	0 0.0%	4 4.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	15 16.9%	2 2.2%	0 0.0%	2 2.2%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	9 10.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	
	Red 8	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	29 10.9%	2 2.2%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	5 5.6%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	1 1.1%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 2.2%	4 4.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	
Target Class	94.1%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	99.6%	50.0%	85.7%	100%	85.7%	100%	100%	83.3%	62.5%	71.4%	100%	71.4%	85.7%	72.7%	100%	81.8%	66.7%		
5.9%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	50.0%	14.3%	0.0%	14.3%	0.0%	0.0%	16.7%	37.5%	28.6%	0.0%	28.6%	14.3%	27.3%	0.0%	18.2%	33.3%		

C

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix								(b) Validation Confusion Matrix								(c) Test Confusion Matrix							
Output Class	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	
	Green	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
	White	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Red ½	0	0	45	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0
	Red 1	0	0	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	0	0
	Red 2	0	0	0	0	26	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	8	0	0	0	0	0	1	7	0	0	0	0
	Red 4	0	0	0	0	0	44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	0	0
	Red 6	0	0	0	0	0	0	49	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0
	Red 8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0
	Accuracy	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	75.0%	57.1%	91.7%	93.8%	88.9%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	80.0%
Loss	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	25.0%	42.9%	8.3%	6.2%	11.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	12.5%	

D

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix								(b) Validation Confusion Matrix								(c) Test Confusion Matrix							
Output Class	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	
	Green	18	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
	White	0	16	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	2	0	0	0	1	0
	Red ½	0	0	4	37	0	0	0	0	0	2	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	9	0	0	0	0
	Red 1	0	0	0	1	37	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	1	0	0	0
	Red 2	0	0	0	0	0	24	0	0	0	0	0	3	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	8	0	0	0
	Red 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	42	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0
	Red 6	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	48	1	0	0	0	0	2	9	1	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0
	Red 8	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	29	0	1	1	0	0	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0
	Accuracy	78.3%	80.0%	92.5%	100%	100%	100%	98.0%	96.7%	83.3%	57.1%	81.2%	84.2%	100%	80.0%	90.0%	83.3%	83.1%	85.7%	71.4%	81.8%	81.8%	100%	95.2%	82.4%
Loss	21.7%	20.0%	7.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	2.0%	3.3%	16.7%	42.9%	18.8%	15.8%	0.0%	20.0%	10.0%	16.7%	16.9%	14.3%	28.6%	18.2%	18.2%	0.0%	4.8%	17.6%	

b. BPSO:

Table 7: Results of SOM Neural Network Classification for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by: (A) BPSO-LDA, (B) BPSO-NBC, (C) BPSO-SVM, and (D) BPSO-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

A

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix								(b) Validation Confusion Matrix								(c) Test Confusion Matrix							
Output Class	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	
	Green	16	0	0	0	0	0	4	2	6	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	4	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
	White	0	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	0	1	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Red ½	0	0	5	33	0	0	0	0	0	1	8	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	18	0	1	0	0	0
	Red 1	0	0	0	0	35	0	0	0	0	0	2	15	1	1	0	0	0	0	16	1	1	0	0	0
	Red 2	0	0	0	0	0	27	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	9	0	0	0	0
	Red 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	46	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	0
	Red 6	1	0	0	0	0	0	48	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	11	1	0	0
	Red 8	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	28	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	1	0	1	0	2	0
	Accuracy	84.2%	77.3%	100%	100%	100%	100%	92.3%	90.3%	54.5%	75.0%	53.3%	100%	75.0%	94.7%	83.3%	66.7%	77.5%	66.7%	87.5%	94.7%	94.1%	81.8%	84.6%	91.7%
Loss	15.8%	22.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	7.7%	9.7%	45.5%	25.0%	46.7%	0.0%	25.0%	5.3%	16.7%	33.3%	22.5%	33.3%	12.5%	5.3%	5.9%	18.2%	15.4%	8.3%	

B

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix									(b) Validation Confusion Matrix									(c) Test Confusion Matrix								
		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	
Output Class	Green	18	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	78.3%	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	50.0%	4	0	0	0	0	0	2	4	40.0%
	White	0	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%	0	6	6	0	0	0	0	1	46.2%	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	50.0%
	Red ½	0	1	36	0	0	0	0	0	97.3%	1	1	13	0	0	0	0	1	81.2%	0	2	9	0	0	0	0	1	75.0%
	Red 1	0	0	0	42	0	0	0	0	100%	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	100%	0	0	0	8	5	0	0	0	61.5%
	Red 2	0	0	0	0	23	0	0	0	100%	0	0	0	1	6	0	0	0	85.7%	0	0	0	2	8	0	0	0	80.0%
	Red 4	0	0	0	0	0	45	0	0	100%	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	0	100%	0	0	0	0	18	1	0	0	94.7%
	Red 6	2	0	0	0	0	0	46	1	93.9%	3	0	0	0	0	0	9	1	69.2%	3	0	0	0	0	0	12	2	70.6%
	Red 8	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	83.3%	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	8	88.9%	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	50.0%
			81.8%	95.7%	100%	100%	100%	88.5%	90.9%	85.1%	33.3%	85.7%	65.0%	93.3%	100%	92.9%	100%	66.7%	79.8%	50.0%	50.0%	81.8%	80.0%	61.5%	94.7%	80.0%	22.2%	70.8%
			18.2%	4.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	11.5%	9.1%	4.9%	66.7%	14.3%	35.0%	6.7%	0.0%	7.1%	0.0%	33.3%	20.2%	50.0%	50.0%	18.2%	20.0%	38.5%	5.3%	20.0%	77.8%	29.2%

C

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix									(b) Validation Confusion Matrix									(c) Test Confusion Matrix								
		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	
Output Class	Green	11	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	91.7%	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%	4	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	80.0%
	White	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	2	66.7%	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%
	Red ½	0	8	36	0	0	0	0	5	73.5%	0	5	14	0	0	0	0	3	63.6%	0	2	8	0	0	0	0	2	66.7%
	Red 1	0	0	3	34	5	0	0	0	81.0%	0	0	0	17	0	0	0	0	100%	0	0	2	10	3	2	0	0	58.8%
	Red 2	0	0	0	1	12	8	1	9	95.7%	0	0	0	19	1	0	0	0	100%	0	0	0	0	11	2	0	0	41.2%
	Red 4	0	0	0	0	5	19	0	0	79.2%	0	0	0	1	5	0	0	0	83.3%	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	100%
	Red 6	0	0	0	0	0	1	46	1	79.3%	0	0	0	0	0	12	2	0	85.7%	0	0	0	0	0	16	1	1	88.9%
	Red 8	10	0	0	0	0	1	46	1	79.3%	5	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	61.5%	2	0	0	0	0	1	15	0	83.3%
			50.0%	60.0%	92.3%	87.2%	79.2%	97.9%	95.8%	73.1%	37.5%	44.4%	87.5%	94.4%	100%	100%	72.7%	50.0%	76.4%	66.7%	60.0%	66.7%	100%	76.9%	84.2%	88.2%	57.1%	78.7%
			50.0%	40.0%	7.7%	12.8%	20.8%	2.1%	4.2%	26.9%	62.5%	55.6%	12.5%	5.6%	0.0%	0.0%	27.3%	50.0%	23.6%	33.3%	40.0%	33.3%	0.0%	23.1%	15.8%	11.8%	42.9%	21.3%

D

		(a) Training Confusion Matrix									(b) Validation Confusion Matrix									(c) Test Confusion Matrix								
		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8		Green	White	Red ½	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	
Output Class	Green	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100%
	White	0	19	0	0	0	0	0	0	95.0%	0	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	80.0%	0	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	85.7%
	Red ½	0	0	43	0	0	0	0	1	97.7%	0	3	6	0	0	0	0	0	66.7%	1	2	13	0	0	0	0	0	81.2%
	Red 1	0	0	0	16	2	0	0	1	97.7%	0	0	2	14	1	0	0	0	82.4%	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	100%
	Red 2	0	0	0	0	16	2	0	0	97.7%	0	0	0	2	14	1	0	0	17.6%	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	100%
	Red 4	0	0	0	0	25	0	0	0	100%	0	0	0	1	11	0	0	0	91.7%	0	0	0	2	5	0	0	0	71.4%
	Red 6	0	0	0	0	0	45	0	0	100%	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	100%	0	0	0	0	0	13	0	0	100%
	Red 8	2	0	0	0	0	0	45	0	95.7%	2	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	87.5%	1	0	0	0	0	0	17	1	89.5%
			83.3%	100%	97.7%	100%	100%	100%	92.3%	97.7%	0	0	0	0	1	0	5	0	83.3%	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	11	84.6%
			16.7%	0.0%	2.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	7.7%	2.3%	75.0%	57.1%	66.7%	93.3%	91.7%	94.7%	100%	100%	87.6%	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.1%	0.0%	12.4%	15.4%

c. ACO:

Table 8: Results of SOM Neural Network Classification for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by: (A) ACO-LDA, (B) ACO-NBC, (C) ACO-SVM, and (D) ACO-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

A

Output Class	(a) Training Confusion Matrix								(b) Validation Confusion Matrix								(c) Test Confusion Matrix							
	Green	White	Red %	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red %	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red %	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8
Green	13	2	0	0	0	0	2	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	7	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
White	0	16	5	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	6	0	0	0	0	1
Red %	0	0	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	5	0	0	0	0	0
Red 1	0	0	0	38	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	4	0	0	0
Red 2	0	0	0	0	22	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	1	0	0
Red 4	0	0	0	0	0	52	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0
Red 6	8	1	1	0	0	0	41	3	3	0	0	0	0	15	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	17	2	
Red 8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	1	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	9
Green %	61.9%	80.0%	83.8%	100%	78.6%	98.1%	95.3%	80.0%	42.9%	57.1%	78.9%	71.4%	85.7%	100%	93.8%	40.0%	87.5%	71.4%	45.5%	73.3%	42.9%	90.9%	100%	69.2%
White %	38.1%	20.0%	16.2%	0.0%	21.4%	1.9%	4.7%	20.0%	57.1%	42.9%	21.1%	28.6%	14.3%	0.0%	6.2%	60.0%	12.5%	28.6%	54.5%	26.7%	57.1%	9.1%	0.0%	30.8%

B

Output Class	(a) Training Confusion Matrix								(b) Validation Confusion Matrix								(c) Test Confusion Matrix							
	Green	White	Red %	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red %	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red %	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8
Green	2	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	2	4	
White	0	12	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	
Red %	0	0	11	32	0	0	0	2	0	2	14	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	10	0	0	0	0	
Red 1	0	0	0	0	36	2	1	0	0	0	2	10	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	12	0	0	0	
Red 2	0	0	0	0	0	26	0	0	0	0	0	2	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	9	0	0	
Red 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	45	0	0	0	1	0	0	19	1	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	
Red 6	14	0	0	0	0	0	1	42	2	2	0	0	0	0	8	1	7	0	0	0	0	18	1	
Red 8	5	0	2	0	0	0	0	19	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	1	0	1	0	0	0	5	
Green %	9.5%	52.2%	88.9%	87.8%	92.9%	95.7%	91.3%	82.6%	16.7%	75.0%	77.8%	83.3%	100%	95.0%	80.0%	80.0%	11.1%	66.7%	76.9%	85.7%	100%	100%	90.0%	
White %	90.5%	47.8%	11.1%	12.2%	7.1%	4.3%	8.7%	17.4%	83.3%	25.0%	22.2%	16.7%	0.0%	5.0%	20.0%	40.0%	88.9%	33.3%	23.1%	14.3%	0.0%	0.0%	10.0%	

C

Output Class	(a) Training Confusion Matrix								(b) Validation Confusion Matrix								(c) Test Confusion Matrix							
	Green	White	Red %	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red %	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8	Green	White	Red %	Red 1	Red 2	Red 4	Red 6	Red 8
Green	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
White	0	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	3	0	0	0	0	0
Red %	0	0	38	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	17	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	8	0	0	0	0	0
Red 1	0	0	0	45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	11	0	2	0	0
Red 2	0	0	0	0	27	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	0	0	0
Red 4	0	0	0	0	0	45	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	0
Red 6	0	0	0	0	0	0	45	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	16	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	14	0
Red 8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0
Green %	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	60.0%	55.6%	94.4%	77.8%	100%	100%	94.1%	75.0%	84.6%	75.0%	72.7%	84.6%	100%	88.9%	100%	100%
White %	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	40.0%	44.4%	5.6%	22.2%	0.0%	0.0%	5.9%	25.0%	15.4%	25.0%	27.3%	15.4%	0.0%	11.1%	0.0%	0.0%

D

2. ROC curves:

a. BGWO:

A

B

C

D

Figure 30: ROC curve of SOM Neural Network classifier for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by genetic algorithms (A) BGWO-LDA, (B) BGWO-NBC, (C) BGWO-SVM, and (D) BGWO-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

b. BPSO:

A

B

Figure 31: ROC curve of SOM Neural Network classifier for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by genetic algorithms (A) BPSO-LDA, (B) BPSO-NBC, (C) BPSO-SVM, and (D) BPSO-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

c. ACO:

A

B

C

D

Figure 32: ROC curve of SOM Neural Network classifier for the maturity process of strawberry spectra at wavenumbers selected by genetic algorithms (A) ACO-LDA, (B) ACO-NBC, (C) ACO-SVM, and (D) ACO-DTC shown by: (a) Training confusion matrix (60% of spectra), (b) Validation confusion matrix (20% of spectra), (c) Test confusion matrix (20% of spectra).

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